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CONSTRUCTING INITIAL DATA FOR BINARY NEUTRON STARS
USING THE EINSTEIN TOOLKIT

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RELATORE:

PROF.SSA ELOISA BENTIVEGNA

CORRELATORE:

DOTT. WOLFGANG KASTAUN

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Abstract

This report focuses on the thesis work which has been carried out in order to construct initial data for binary neutron stars. The work, which has been completed with the collaboration of Prof. Eloisa Bentivegna of the Department of Physics and Astronomy of the University of Catania and Prof. Bruno Giacomazzo and Dr. Wolfgang Kastaun of the Department of Physics of the University of Trento, has required the deployment of the public code “Einstein Toolkit”, and, in particular, the `CT_MULTILEVEL` solver which it comprises.

The first chapter represents an introduction to the scientific context in which the work is included and the methods used; a description of the entire research project is also included, with a focus on the various steps which have been executed.

In the second chapter, an introduction to the astrophysics of compact objects is presented. In particular, neutron stars are treated, focusing on the most important historical discoveries centered on them and the description of their birth.

The relativistic treatment of neutron stars is described in the third chapter, preceded by a brief description of the general theory of relativity, together with the most important mathematical and physical considerations about said theory. At the end of the chapter, gravitational waves, which these objects can emit, are briefly discussed.

In the fourth chapter, the ADM formulation of Einstein’s equations is treated in detail; modern applications of the formulation are also shown.

The fifth chapter characterizes the numerical methods employed, together with particular applications carried out in the context of the thesis work.

Applications of the methods, together with the results of the work are presented in the sixth chapter, where the single star case and the binary case are treated separately.

Conclusions about the work are given in the last chapter.

Chapter 1

Introduction

In 1915 Albert Einstein predicted, in the context of his general theory of relativity, the existence of gravitational waves, ripples in the fabric of spacetime which reach Earth at the speed of light after their origination during cosmic cataclysms which happen in the distant universe. Although, during the 20th century, many experiments have proven the rightness of the theory, gravitational waves had not been detected.

On 14 September 2015, the first observation of gravitational waves has been made: the signal, which has been named *GW150914*, was detected by the LIGO detectors in Hanford, Washington state, and Livingston, Louisiana, USA and has represented the first observation of the merger of a pair of black holes of around 36 and 29 solar masses and the subsequent “ringdown” of the single resulting black hole. Therefore, gravitational wave detectors such as LIGO or Virgo, which have operated for several years, have gained considerable importance; currently, there are plans for the construction of several other detectors. Among the most promising sources for these detectors, the coalescences of binary neutron star systems represent the only binary systems of compact objects with known electromagnetic counterparts observed so far, because of the electromagnetic waves from binary pulsar observations.

In order to make predictions about the latest orbits before the collapse of the system to a single object, numerical simulations of the Einstein field equations are required. Even before, in order to start these simulations, realistic initial data, which describe the system different orbits before the merger, are needed. From the simulation of binary neutron star mergers one can determine a gravitational waveform, with which it is possible to better understand the extreme conditions of the degenerate gas these objects are made of, starting from their equation of state, which represents the way thermodynamic variables such as pressure and density are related; in particular, with the revelation of the waves and the comparison

with ready-made models, we might arrive at better conclusions about the mass limit of these stars, the short gamma ray bursts, the nuclear processes that occur in these stars and so on. Unlike other methods, which use approximations of the Einstein field equations, numerical simulations treat them directly and represent the best-known method to determine gravitational signals. In order to make possible an accurate gravitational wave astronomy, the latter have to be modeled as realistic and precise as possible [Tichy, 2012 - Moldenhauer et al. 2014].

The thesis work here presented, which represents a collaboration between the Department of Physics and Astronomy of the University of Catania and the Department of Physics of the University of Trento, concerns the construction and application of initial data for binary neutron star systems, employing the open-source software “Einstein Toolkit”, using a specific solver, included in the same software, for elliptic partial differential equations.

The progress has begun at the Department of Physics of the University of Catania, under the supervision of Professor Eloisa Bentivegna, in May 2016. For several months before, an initial training on numerical methods for partial differential equations of general relativity, which included the creation of programs that apply the finite difference method to the resolution of the one-dimensional wave equation, with fixed initial and periodic boundary conditions, and the subsequent application of convergence test methods for the solution, has been carried out. This work, initially performed as a standalone C code, was then run again employing the Einstein Toolkit software, by modifying existing modules of the same.

A number of preparatory meetings, about the methods and the specific modules, which would later be used, followed this first phase; particular attention was paid to the previously mentioned solver, of which Prof. Bentivegna is the author. The latter, present within the software under the name `CT_MULTILEVEL`, solves generic elliptic differential equations with a multigrid approach, adopting a non-linear Gauss-Seidel relaxation algorithm and accessing different grids by FullMultiGrid (FMG) mode.

The central part of the work was carried out in the following months at the Department of Physics of the University of Trento, under the coordination of Prof. Bruno Giacomazzo and Dr. Wolfgang Kastaun. The group has therefore initially proceeded to the construction of initial data in the case of a single neutron star, using the TOVSTAR program, adaptable as a non-public module for Einstein Toolkit software, developed by Dr. Kastaun. The latter solves the Tolman-Oppenheimer-Volkoff (TOV) equation for the astrophysical object involved, represented by a non-rotating ideal fluid; the input is given by the equation of state (in barotropic form) and the central density. The program includes several features, including the ability to add a slow rotation to the object, to compute the mass-radius

diagram and to select the reference system to use. The following step was to extend this program in order to create the superposition of two objects; therefore, changes were made to the code in order to properly perform the overlap, point by point in the grids, of the hydrodynamic and relativistic variables.

The next phase of work has concerned the implementation of the results determined using TOVSTAR to the CT_MULTILEVEL solver, optimizing the setup of the grid and solving the parameters in order to achieve the desired convergence. In fact, the former results are only to be considered as an initial guess of a subsequent refinement: the CT_MULTILEVEL module fulfills this task by considering the “Conformal Thin Sandwich” formulation of the Einstein field equations and iteratively solving, with the methods described before, the latter.

The work will enable the generation of NS initial data in more general configurations, giving an original contribution to this field; in fact, the initial data computed by TOVSTAR are not directly given as an input to the solver but are initially stored into other Cactus modules, such as “HydroBase” and “ADMBase”, which work as an interface between the two. Therefore, other programs (provided they can communicate with the interface modules) may also be used in the future in order to create initial data subsequently refined with CT_MULTILEVEL.

After an introduction about the most important discoveries and the astrophysical aspects regarding neutron stars, the relativistic treatment of their equilibrium is described: in this regard, General Relativity is initially presented, and afterwards the particular mathematical treatment is described in detail. The 4th chapter focuses on the ADM formulation of the Einstein field equations, which represents one of the foundations of numerical relativity and, in general, of the modern theory of relativity. The numerical methods which have been used are then explained in detail, together with the particular formulation of General Relativity adopted in the context of the research project. The 6th chapter describes the particular work carried out, together with qualitative and quantitative results; in 7th chapter, conclusions about the entire project are given.

Chapter 2

Neutron stars

2.1 Compact objects: an introduction

Neutron stars represent one of the possible results at the very end of stellar evolution. They are, together with white dwarfs and black holes, classified as compact objects (due to their high *compactness*, parameter which is determined by the ratio mass/radius M/R of the object), which subsequently gives rise to the “special” nature of the matter in these stellar remnants. All the three species differ profoundly from normal stars: they do not burn nuclear fuel, so cannot support themselves against gravitational collapse by generating thermal pressure. The support, respectively for white dwarfs and neutron stars, comes from the pressure of degenerate electrons or neutrons; black holes are, instead, completely collapsed stars, i.e. stars that could not find any means to hold back the inward pull of gravity and therefore collapsed to singularities. Compact objects also differ from normal stars because they have much smaller radii (up to $10^{-5}R_{\odot}$ for neutron stars) and much higher densities, as shown in Fig. 1.

Depending on their mass, stars reach the end of their evolution as a white dwarf, neutron star or black hole; white dwarfs originate from stars with masses $M \leq 4M_{\odot}$ and have a maximum mass limit of about $1.4M_{\odot}$ (the Chandrasekhar limit). On the other hand, neutron stars, which also have a maximum mass in the range of $1.4 - 3M_{\odot}$ (the Tolman-Oppenheimer-Volkoff limit), and black holes originate from more massive stars; the final evolution of these stars, however, is poorly understood. It is believed that the most massive stars form black holes, while massive stars with a mass below a certain limit form neutron stars. It is important to notice that white dwarfs and neutron stars can also become black holes if they exceed the respective limit mass (this could happen, for example,

Fig. 1 - Compact objects in the Universe at large (Shapiro S., Teukolsky S. 1983).

by accretion of the gas within a binary system). The particularly large surface potentials (shown in Table 1) encountered in compact objects imply that general relativity is important in determining their structure.

Table 1 - Noteworthy physical quantities of compact objects (Shapiro S., Teukolsky S. 1983)

Object	Mass (M)	Radius (R)	Mean Density ($g\ cm^{-3}$)	Surface Potential (GM/Rc^2)
White dwarf	$\leq M_{\odot}$	$\sim 10^{-2}R_{\odot}$	$\leq 10^7$	$\sim 10^{-4}$
Neutron star	$\sim 1 - 3M_{\odot}$	$\sim 10^{-5}R_{\odot}$	$\leq 10^{15}$	$\sim 10^{-1}$
Black hole	Arbitrary	$2GM/c^2$	$\sim M/R^3$	1

From now on, particular attention will only be given to neutron stars; these objects represent exceptional laboratories both for studying matter in ultra-dense conditions and for probing gravitational waves.

2.2 Neutron stars: The idea and the discovery

In 1934, Walter Baade and Fritz Zwicky proposed the existence of neutron stars, just one year after the discovery of the neutron by James Chadwick. In order to give an explanation for the origin of a supernova, they proposed supernova explosions as the phenomena which occur when ordinary stars are turned into neutron stars, pointing also out these would be at very high density and small radius, and would be much more gravitationally bound than ordinary stars.

In 1939, J. Robert Oppenheimer and George Volkoff, assuming matter to be composed of an ideal gas of free neutrons at high density, made the first calculation of neutron star models. Neutron stars were believed to be too faint to be detectable, so little work was done on them until until 1960s.

In 1967, with the newly installed Mullard Radio Astronomy Observatory just outside Cambridge, graduate student Jocelyn Bell and her advisor Antony Hewish discovered regular radio pulses (with a period of about 1.3 seconds) from CP 1919.

One year later, the Cambridge radio astronomy group announced in two papers (February and April 1968) the startling observations of rapidly recurring short radio pulses from four sources in the sky; Thomas Gold (1968) proposed they were rotating neutron stars, and this is generally accepted today. The discoveries of the Crab and Vela *pulsars* (portmanteau of pulsating stars), both of which situated in supernova remnants, in the late fall of the same year, provided evidence for the formation of neutron stars in supernova explosions. Research and theoretical work on neutron stars was further stimulated by the discovery of pulsating, compact X-ray sources (“X-ray pulsars”) by the UHURU satellite in 1971. These are believed to be rotating hot neutron stars, the energy source is gravitational and results from a rain of gas falling onto the surface of the neutron star from a companion star or the interstellar medium.

In 1974, year in which Antony Hewish was awarded the Nobel Prize in Physics “for his decisive role in the discovery of pulsars”, Joseph Taylor and Russel Hulse discovered the first binary pulsar, PSR B1913+16, which consists of two neutron stars, of which only one seen as a pulsar, orbiting around their center of mass. This discovery provides an opportunity to test for the existence of gravitational radiation: indeed, Einstein’s general theory of relativity predicts that the orbit of the two massive objects decays with time, as they emit gravitational radiation. The observation of this phenomenon earned Hulse and Taylor the Nobel Prize in Physics in 1993. Another important discovery came ten years later, with the observation, by the radio astronomer Marta Burgay and colleagues at the Parkes Observatory, of the first (and still the only known) double pulsar system, PSR J0737-3039. At present, over 1500 pulsars have been observed, together with a small number of non pulsating neutron stars.

2.3 The birth of neutron stars

The majority of the stars (about 90 percent of the stars observed in the universe, including the sun) are main sequence stars. These stars are characterized by hydrostatic equilibrium, i.e. the inward force of gravity is balanced by the outward force of the thermal pressure gas, the source of energy being nuclear energy, whose generation through reactions of hydrogen conversion into helium happens primarily in their central regions. Main sequence stars show then a chemical composition gradient, although the time variation of this gradient is different, depending on the mass of the star analyzed. Low-mass stars (say $0.1M_{\odot} < M < 1M_{\odot}$), which have a radiative core, have a continuous and monotone gradient: hydrogen burns more rapidly in the innermost regions of the star and less when moving outwardly; therefore, the higher the density, the faster the burning. For instance, a solar-mass star consisting to 72% ca. of hydrogen, burns less than 10% of its mass in $11.4 \cdot 10^9$ years ca.

In more massive stars, the convective core continuously mixes any chemical composition difference; the nucleus will then have a uniform chemical composition at any time of its evolution (an example is shown in Fig. 2). Therefore, when there is no more hydrogen to burn, this happens at the same time everywhere.

Fig. 2 - Evolution of the mass fraction of helium as a function of the mass fraction m/M within high mass stars. The solid line represents the hydrogen profile X_H for a $5M_{\odot}$ star at the end of hydrogen burning in a shrinking convective core. The dashed lines represent the hydrogen content levels in the core at the onset 0, and two intermediate levels 1 and 2 (Kippenhahn and Weigert, 1990).

The evolution of the internal structure of a $5M_{\odot}$ star, from the main sequence phase to the formation of the C-O core, as explained later, is shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3 - The evolution of the internal structure of a star of $5M_{\odot}$ of extreme population I is represented in the upper diagram. The abscissa shows the age of the star after the ignition of hydrogen in units of 10^7 years; the different layers are characterized by their value of m/M . The cloudy regions indicate convective areas. In the lower diagram, the corresponding positions of the star, denoted with the same letters used in the upper one, are represented on the H-R diagram at each stage of its evolution (Kippenhahn and Weigert, 1990).

At the starting point A, the star begins its lifetime on the main sequence: at this point, the core contains $\sim 20\%$ of the mass of the star, although hydrogen burning happens within the inner 7% . After the first $5.6 \cdot 10^7$ years, in which the star roughly remains at the same location on the H-R diagram, it evolves to point B and then to point C, which corresponds to the time in which the central hydrogen fuel is exhausted. At this point, an isothermal helium core is formed and begins to collapse, while the envelope rapidly expands and forms a giant star. From point C to point D, hydrogen burning is not over, but continues in a shell around the helium core. At the point D, the star reaches its Hayashi track and another convection region is formed in the envelope. When stage E is reached,

the temperature of the core, which continues to increase due to the contraction of the central regions, makes possible the helium burning process, in which three helium-4 atoms combine to form one carbon-12 atom, releasing energy through γ radiation during the process (also known as *triple-alpha* process). The star, increasing its temperature, moves then to point F. Helium burning continues until point G, where there is no more helium in the central regions and an isothermal ^{12}C core is formed; helium burning, however, is not over and continues in shells around the isothermal core. By point H, oxygen also begins to be produced in the innermost regions, as the result of ^4He reacting with ^{12}C ; this point also coincides with the end of hydrogen burning, which, after point D, continues in shells with larger and larger radii. At point K, the star cools down and develops another convection zone.

More massive stars continue producing heavier and heavier nuclei, starting with the silicon production from carbon and oxygen burning. The final result for very massive stars is represented by the well-known “onion-skin” structure with a central core of iron peak elements and successive shells of silicon, carbon and oxygen, helium and hydrogen. After the synthesis of iron, the most stable of the chemical elements, the star can’t proceed any further with the synthesis of heavier elements through nuclear burning. For elements lighter than iron, in fact, nuclear fusion releases energy, while consumes energy for heavier elements. The more massive the star, the more rapidly it evolves through the stages and, if the star is massive enough (say $M \geq 8M_{\odot}$) a *supernova* explosion becomes possible: the star as a whole explodes and ejects its outer layers at great velocity, giving rise to the formation of supernova remnants.

Supernovae are relatively rare events: in fact, estimates for the supernova rate in the Milky Way Galaxy give about 3 per century, so that we expect 60 supernova remnants younger than 2000 yr, while only five supernovae have been observed during the last millennium, the most recent detected being SN 1987A, which exploded in the Large Magellanic Cloud in 1987. During these events an extremely high luminosity, which can be as great as that of a small galaxy, is reached. Supernovae are classified into two types, *I* and *II*, and different subtypes, depending, respectively, from the absence or presence of the Balmer series of hydrogen in their optical spectra; while type *Ia* supernovae are believed to originate from the mass accretion and subsequent excess of Chandrasekhar limit of a white dwarf star (which can happen in binary systems), all the other types (type *II*, *Ib*, *Ic*, etc.) are associated with the core collapse of massive stars. During the iron core collapse, two important processes, which rob the core of energy, hastening its collapse, kick in: photodisintegration and neutronization.

The previous one, which can be written schematically as

is related to the disintegration of heavy iron nuclei by high energy thermal photons, resulting into He, protons and neutrons. With the latter, free protons and electrons fuse into neutrons and neutrinos (which can then escape, carrying energy away from the star), through inverse β -process

For a $15M_{\odot}$ star, the iron core collapse, which only lasts approximately 1 second, leaves a neutron star with a temperature of over $7.1 \cdot 10^9 K$ and a density of over $7.3 \cdot 10^9$ (Woosley and Janka, 2005). During the first 10^3 years, the temperature of the new formed neutron star eventually falls to around 10^6 kelvin (as it has been observed for the crab pulsar, Fig.4), principally due to neutrino cooling processes.

Fig. 4 - A composite image of the Crab Nebula, at the center of which the Pulsar is visible, showing the X-ray (blue), and optical (red) images superimposed (Hester et al. 2002).

Chapter 3

Relativistic stars and their equilibrium

3.1 General Relativity: an introduction

General Relativity is the theory of gravitation developed by Albert Einstein and published in 1916. Generally considered Einstein's masterwork, it is an extension of his theory of Special Relativity, which he published eleven years before.

Special Relativity is based on two postulates: the principle of *relativity*, stating that the laws of physics are the same for all nonaccelerating observers, and the *universality of the speed of light*, according to which the speed of light in a vacuum never changes, even if the the light source, or the observer, is moving. One can prove that, starting from these hypotheses, the well-known equation $E = mc^2$ which relates energy and mass, can be determined, together with other important results such as *time dilatation*, i.e. the fact that a fast moving observer measures time passing more slowly with respect to a relatively stationary observer, and *length contraction*, according to which a fast moving object appears shorter along the direction of motion relative to a slow-moving one. The groundbreaking ideas of relative times and spaces are also accompanied by the unification into a four-dimensional "space-time".

General Relativity is Einstein's theory of gravity which can be regarded as a mathematical extension of Special Relativity. General Relativity explains gravitation as a consequence of the curvature of spacetime, which it acquires due to the presence of massive bodies, as represented as a curved rubber sheet in Fig.5. On the other hand, spacetime curvature affects the movement of matter,

which reciprocally determines the geometric properties and evolution of spacetime; John Wheeler’s famous quotation: “Spacetime tells matter how to move; matter tells spacetime how to curve.” can be considered as a succinct summary of this connection between mass and spacetime.

Fig. 5 - Representation of the spacetime curvature which the presence of a massive body determines.

The Einstein field equations represent the core of Einstein’s general theory of relativity: similarly to Maxwell’s equations, which describe how the electromagnetic fields are determined from the sources, i.e. charges and currents, the Einstein field equations determine how the geometry of the spacetime is influenced by the present matter. The latter, which will be better described in the next chapter, are very difficult to solve and few exact solutions are known to date: historically first of these is the Schwarzschild solution, which will be better treated later, found by Karl Schwarzschild a few months after Einstein’s publication.

Einstein also proposed three tests of General Relativity (subsequently called the “classical” tests) in 1916. The first of these tests, the only one already known prior to Einstein’s publication, regarded the explanation of the anomalous rate of the perihelion of Mercury’s orbit: in fact, in the 19th century it was discovered that the presence of the other planets of the solar system, which perturb Mercury’s orbit, cannot fully account for the turning rate of its orbit. Einstein showed that General Relativity can entirely explain the observed amount of perihelion shift. The second important confirmation happened in 1919, when sir Arthur Eddington proved Einstein’s prediction for the deflection of starlight by the Sun during the total solar eclipse of May 29. Later, more precise experiments have unambiguously shown that the amount of deflection agrees with the prediction of General Relativity. The third test, proposed in 1959 and then conducted by Robert Pound and his graduate student Glen A. Rebka, has regarded proving gravitational redshift, i.e. a change of the frequency of the electromagnetic radiation as it passes through a gravitational field. Although this test, later known as the “Pound–Rebka experiment”, represents the last of the classical tests, many others, related for example to the detection of gravitational waves which origin from compact object mergers, are still in progress.

3.2 The mathematics of General Relativity

General Relativity is a geometric theory of gravity, according to which the latter arises from the curvature of the spacetime. This unification of space and time is mathematically represented as a four-dimensional, smooth, connected manifold equipped with a Lorentzian metric, while the mathematical theory which better represents the whole General Relativity is differential geometry. For every spacetime, geometrically characterized by its metric, one can express the following line element, representing an infinitesimal displacement between two points of the metric space:

$$ds^2 = g_{\alpha\beta} dx^\alpha dx^\beta \quad (3.1)$$

where the indices α and β run over 0, 1, 2, 3 and Einstein summation convention, which shortens the notation by assuming an implied sum over repeated indices, is intended. The term $g_{\alpha\beta}$ represents the $\alpha - \beta$ component of the metric tensor; the latter is the fundamental object of study of general relativity that can be thought as a generalization of the euclidean distance to the four-dimensional spacetime, accounting for the presence of time.

The simplest metric, referring to a flat spacetime, is the Minkowski metric with components $\eta_{\alpha\beta} = \mathbf{diag}(-1, +1, +1, +1)$. In general, however, spacetime is curved due to the presence of massive objects, as already discussed in the previous chapter; in particular, the laws of physics must be expressed in a form that is valid independently of any coordinate system used to label points in spacetime. This justifies the use of tensors in general relativity; the purpose is in fact to make equations in order to represent theory in a coordinate-independent way.

General Relativity is based on four fundamental points:

- **The spacetime representation**, i.e. space and time can be described via a spacetime, a four-dimensional manifold with a metric of Lorentzian signature.
- **The measurability of the metric**, which expresses the fact that the metric tensor is not a completely abstract entity, but instead describes physical aspects of the spacetime such as lengths and time intervals, and as such its value can be measured via rods and clocks.
- **The Local Flatness Theorem**, stating that physics in the neighborhood of any point can be described by a flat spacetime, i.e. a spacetime equipped with a Minkowski metric. This is also equivalent to say that one can always construct a local inertial frame at the neighborhood of any event, or also that the effects of curvature cannot be measured locally.

- **The Equivalence Principle**, which states that any law that can be expressed via a tensor equation in Special Relativity holds in the same form in General Relativity.

The core of the general theory of relativity is undoubtedly represented by the Einstein field equations, which constitute a set of 10 differential equations characterized by the following writing:

$$R_{\alpha\beta} - \frac{1}{2}Rg_{\alpha\beta} = 8\pi T_{\alpha\beta} \quad (3.2)$$

In addition to the metric tensor $g_{\alpha\beta}$, two other rank-2 symmetric tensors appear: the Ricci curvature tensor $R_{\alpha\beta}$ and the stress-energy tensor $T_{\alpha\beta}$. The former expresses the curvature of the considered manifold; if contracted with the metric tensor it results in the scalar curvature R , so that $R = R_{\alpha\beta}g^{\alpha\beta}$. The latter is a tensor quantity which describes the density and flux of energy and momentum in a given portion of the spacetime, accounting for the presence of matter, radiation etc. An example of such a tensor is represented by the following perfect fluid case, which is generally used in order to model matter distributions

$$T_{\alpha\beta} = (\rho + p)u_{\alpha}u_{\beta} + pg_{\alpha\beta} \quad (3.3)$$

where ρ is the fluid density, p is its pressure and u is the fluid velocity. In an inertial frame of reference comoving with the fluid, better known as the fluid's proper frame of reference, the matrix which represents the tensor assumes the following diagonal form

$$T_{\alpha\beta} = \begin{pmatrix} \rho & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & p & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & p & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & p \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.4)$$

Finally, as all the tensor quantities which appear in eq. (3.2) are symmetric, it appears clear why Einstein's field equations are 10 instead of 16.

3.3 The theory of relativistic stars

Unlike main sequence stars, the outward pressure which balances the inward gravitational force originates from the fermionic nature of neutrons. Neutron stars represent an example of degenerate or Fermi gas, i.e. a gas whose temperature is below the degeneracy temperature, defined as

$$T_F \equiv \frac{\epsilon_F}{K} = \frac{1}{K} \frac{h^2}{8m} \left(\frac{3N}{\pi V} \right)^{\frac{3}{2}} \quad (3.5)$$

in which ϵ_F is the *Fermi energy*, which depends on the mass m of the particles and the particle number density N/V ; K and h represent the Boltzmann and the Planck constant respectively. A simple calculation (Groth, 2002) shows that for a solar mass neutron star with a radius of $10km$, the Fermi temperature is $T_F = 10^{12}K$; therefore, neutron stars can be considered “cold”. Neutrons in a degenerate gas fill up all the possible quantum states up to the Fermi energy, placing the system into its ground state; such a close packing of degenerate fermions, according to the Pauli exclusion principle, which states that two fermions can't occupy the same quantum state, will occupy a volume of finite size. As gravity compresses this finite volume and as neutrons can't get closer, a degenerate gas pressure, which will be better described later, arises and keeps the system at equilibrium.

A description of this status is represented, for non degenerate stars, by the following equation of hydrostatic equilibrium

$$\frac{dP}{dr} = - \frac{GM(r)\rho}{r^2} \quad (3.6)$$

where the left-hand side term of the equation represents the pressure gradient at a distance r from the center of the star; the right-hand side term is related to the inward gravitational force which the mass $M(r)$ of the star acts on a mass element of density ρ . As neutron stars are relativistic stars, however, general relativity instead of classical mechanics has to be used in order to describe their behavior.

The starting point, in this sense, is represented by the description of a metric tensor for a spherically symmetric spacetime. By choosing a description in terms of (t, r, θ, ϕ) , where t is the time coordinate, θ and ϕ represent respectively the polar and the azimuth angle and r is the areal radius, i.e. the radius defined not as the distance from a certain fixed point, but through the area of the constant- r spaces, obtained by integrating $r^2 d\Omega^2$ over the two angular coordinates θ and ϕ . If one also requires that the metric components $g_{t\theta} = g_{t\phi} = g_{r\theta} = g_{r\phi} = 0$, it can be shown that the four-dimensional line element has the following form

$$ds^2 = -g_{tt}dt^2 + 2g_{tr}dtdr + g_{rr}dr^2 + r^2d\theta^2 + r^2\sin^2\theta d\phi^2 \quad (3.7)$$

If the metric tensor does not depend explicitly on time and is also invariant for $t \rightarrow -t$ transformations, and further assuming that both g_{tt} and g_{rr} are positive, the line element reduces to the form

$$ds^2 = -e^{2\Phi} dt^2 + e^{2\Lambda} dr^2 + r^2 d\Omega^2 \quad (3.8)$$

where Λ and Φ are functions of r . Once all the components of the metric tensor are known, one can determine the Christoffel symbols, which are related to the metric components through the following relation¹

$$\Gamma_{\alpha\beta}^{\delta} = \frac{1}{2} g^{\delta\mu} (\partial_{\beta} g_{\alpha\mu} + \partial_{\alpha} g_{\beta\mu} - \partial_{\mu} g_{\alpha\beta}) \quad (3.9)$$

Using (3.8), it can be easily shown that the non-zero Christoffel symbols for this metric are the following

$$\Gamma_{tr}^t = \frac{d\Phi}{dr} \quad (3.10)$$

$$\Gamma_{rr}^r = \frac{d\Lambda}{dr} \quad (3.11)$$

$$\Gamma_{tt}^r = \frac{d\Phi}{dr} e^{2(\Phi-\Lambda)} \quad (3.12)$$

$$\Gamma_{\theta\theta}^r = -e^{-2\Lambda} r \quad (3.13)$$

$$\Gamma_{\phi\phi}^r = -e^{-2\Lambda} r \sin^2\theta \quad (3.14)$$

$$\Gamma_{r\theta}^{\theta} = \Gamma_{r\phi}^{\phi} = \frac{1}{r} \quad (3.15)$$

$$\Gamma_{\phi\phi}^{\theta} = -\sin\theta \cos\theta \quad (3.16)$$

$$\Gamma_{\theta\phi}^{\phi} = \cot\theta \quad (3.17)$$

The non-zero components of the Ricci tensor can now be determined, using the following expression in function of the Christoffel symbols

$$R_{\alpha\beta} = \partial_{\delta} \Gamma_{\alpha\beta}^{\delta} - \partial_{\beta} \Gamma_{\delta\alpha}^{\delta} + \Gamma_{\alpha\beta}^{\lambda} \Gamma_{\lambda\delta}^{\delta} - \Gamma_{\alpha\delta}^{\lambda} \Gamma_{\beta\lambda}^{\delta} \quad (3.18)$$

The only four non-zero components result to be

$$R_{tt} = e^{-2\Lambda+2\Phi} \left[\frac{d^2\Phi}{dr^2} + \left(\frac{d\Phi}{dr} \right)^2 - \frac{d\Lambda}{dr} \frac{d\Phi}{dr} + \frac{2}{r} \frac{d\Phi}{dr} \right] \quad (3.19)$$

$$R_{tt} = - \left[\frac{d^2\Phi}{dr^2} + \left(\frac{d\Phi}{dr} \right)^2 - \frac{d\Lambda}{dr} \frac{d\Phi}{dr} + \frac{2}{r} \frac{d\Lambda}{dr} \right] \quad (3.20)$$

¹From now on, the geometric unit system will be used, so $G = c = 1$; moreover, Greek indices run from 0 to 3, while latin ones run from 1 to 3.

$$R_{\theta\theta} = e^{-2\Lambda} \left[r \left(\frac{d\Lambda}{dr} - \frac{d\Phi}{dr} \right) - 1 \right] + 1 \quad (3.21)$$

$$R_{\phi\phi} = e^{-2\Lambda} \sin^2\theta \left[r \left(\frac{d\Lambda}{dr} - \frac{d\Phi}{dr} \right) - 1 \right] + 1 \quad (3.22)$$

Consequently, one can compute the only four non-zero components of the Einstein tensor, defined as

$$G_{\alpha\beta} \equiv R_{\alpha\beta} - \frac{1}{2} R g_{\alpha\beta} \quad (3.23)$$

where R again represents the scalar curvature;

$$G_{tt} = \frac{1}{r^2} e^{2\Phi} \frac{d}{dr} [r(1 - e^{-2\Lambda})] \quad (3.24)$$

$$G_{rr} = -\frac{1}{r^2} e^{2\Lambda} (1 - e^{-2\Lambda}) + \frac{2}{r} \frac{d\Phi}{dr} \quad (3.25)$$

$$G_{\theta\theta} = r^2 e^{-2\Lambda} \left[\frac{d^2\Phi}{dr^2} + \left(\frac{d\Phi}{dr} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{r} \frac{d\Phi}{dr} - \frac{d\Lambda}{dr} \frac{d\Phi}{dr} - \frac{1}{r} \frac{d\Lambda}{dr} \right] \quad (3.26)$$

$$G_{\phi\phi} = r^2 \sin^2\theta e^{-2\Lambda} \left[\frac{d^2\Phi}{dr^2} + \left(\frac{d\Phi}{dr} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{r} \frac{d\Phi}{dr} - \frac{d\Lambda}{dr} \frac{d\Phi}{dr} - \frac{1}{r} \frac{d\Lambda}{dr} \right] \quad (3.27)$$

A formal simplification can be done by defining the following function

$$m(r) = \frac{1}{2} r (1 - e^{-2\Lambda}) \quad (3.28)$$

The equations (3.24)-(3.27) represent the left-hand side of Einstein's field equations in the "standard" form

$$G_{\alpha\beta} = 8\pi T_{\alpha\beta} \quad (3.29)$$

where $T_{\alpha\beta}$ is again used to express the stress-energy tensor; modeling the star as a spherical distribution of a perfect fluid, with R_* as the radius of the sphere, one can then solve Einstein's field equations both for $r < R_*$ and for $r > R_*$, i.e. respectively inside and outside the star. The only non-zero components (which, however, still vanish when considering the $r > R_*$ region) of such a stress-energy tensor are the following

$$T_{tt} = \rho e^{2\Phi} \quad (3.30)$$

$$T_{rr} = p e^{2\Lambda} \quad (3.31)$$

$$T_{\theta\theta} = p r^2 \quad (3.32)$$

$$T_{\phi\phi} = p r^2 \sin^2\theta \quad (3.33)$$

where p and ρ represent the fluid pressure and rest mass density. Einstein's equa-

tions can then be finally written down; the (t, t) and (r, r) ones imply respectively

$$\frac{dm(r)}{dr} = 4\pi r^2 \rho \quad (3.34)$$

$$\frac{d\Phi}{dr} = \frac{m(r) + 4\pi r^3 \rho}{r[r - 2m(r)]} \quad (3.35)$$

while the (θ, θ) and (ϕ, ϕ) ones both lead to the following equation

$$(\rho + p) \frac{d\Phi}{dr} = -\frac{dp}{dr} \quad (3.36)$$

These equations have to be studied in the two cases $r > R_*$ and $r < R_*$.

In the first case, all the components of the stress-energy are zero; therefore, the equations (3.34) and (3.35) become respectively

$$\frac{dm}{dr} = 0 \quad (3.37)$$

$$\frac{d\Phi}{dr} = \frac{M}{r[r - 2M]} \quad (3.38)$$

where M is the constant such as $m = M = \text{const.}$. The second equation can be solved assuming that the spacetime is asymptotically flat, i.e. tends to the Minkowski one; one obtains then

$$\Phi(r) = \log \sqrt{1 - \frac{2M}{r}} \quad (3.39)$$

The final result is the *Schwarzschild Metric* for a spherically symmetric vacuum spacetime, here expressed in matrix form:

$$g_{\mu\nu} = \begin{pmatrix} -\left(1 - \frac{2M}{r}\right) & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \left(1 - \frac{2M}{r}\right)^{-1} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & r^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & r^2 \sin^2 \theta \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.40)$$

For $r < R_*$, the system can be also integrated. The three equations reduce to (3.34) and the following Tolman–Oppenheimer–Volkov (TOV) equation

$$\frac{dp}{dr} = -\frac{(\rho + p)(m + 4\pi r^3 \rho)}{r(r - 2m)} \quad (3.41)$$

which is obtained by substituting (3.36) in (3.35). If one considers the TOV

equation in the following form, in which the terms G and c are also included,

$$\frac{dp}{dr} = -\frac{G}{r^2} \left[\rho + \frac{p}{c^2} \right] \left[m + 4\pi r^3 \frac{\rho}{c^2} \right] \left[1 - \frac{2Gm}{c^2 r} \right]^{-1} \quad (3.42)$$

it is immediate to recognize that, if the terms of order $1/c^2$ are neglected, i.e. when general-relativistic corrections are not important, the equation becomes the hydrostatic equilibrium equation.

Since (3.34) and (3.41) are two first-order differential equations, two constants of integration are required in order to solve them; in addition, the system of the two equations has to be closed by a third equation which relates p to ρ . This last equation is represented by an equation of state (EOS), usually expressed in the following polytropic form

$$p = K\rho^\Gamma \quad (3.43)$$

where K is the polytropic constant, and Γ the polytropic exponent. The two constants that need to be added are represented by the values of $m(r)$ and $p(r)$ at the center of the star, namely $m_c = m(0) = 0$ and $p_c = p(0)$. As the two functions are continuous everywhere, at the surface of the star their value has to be the following

$$m(R_*) = M \quad (3.44)$$

$$p(R_*) = 0 \quad (3.45)$$

The constant M , which has been introduced while studying the exterior solution, has now the physical meaning of the total mass of the star, obtained by integrating

$$M = \int_0^{R_*} 4\pi\rho r^2 dr \quad (3.46)$$

In some contexts, it may be useful to express the Schwarzschild solution in a conformal form, such as the one determined by Komatsu, Eriguchi and Hachisu (Komatsu et al. 1989), whose metric is represented by the following line element

$$ds^2 = -e^{\gamma+\rho} dt^2 + e^{\gamma-\rho} \bar{r}^2 \sin^2\theta (d\Phi - \omega dt)^2 + e^{2\alpha} (d\bar{r}^2 + \bar{r}^2 d\theta^2) \quad (3.47)$$

where the metric potentials γ , ρ , α and ω depend only on the coordinates \bar{r} and θ . The function $\frac{1}{2}(\gamma + \rho)$ is the relativistic generalization of the Newtonian gravitational potential, while the time dilation factor between an observer moving with angular velocity ω and an observer at infinity is $e^{\frac{1}{2}(\gamma+\rho)}$. In the case of a spherical non-rotating object, the coordinate \bar{r} corresponds to the isotropic Schwarzschild

coordinate, while the exponents are related to \bar{r} through the following relations

$$e^{\frac{1}{2}(\gamma+\rho)} = \frac{1 - M/2\bar{r}}{1 + M/2\bar{r}} \quad (3.48)$$

$$e^{\frac{1}{2}(\gamma-\rho)} = e^\alpha = (1 + 2M/\bar{r})^2 \quad (3.49)$$

3.4 Gravitational waves

The idea of a gravitational radiation carrying away energy and momentum at the expense of the orbital decay of a binary system of two compact objects, subsequently causing the objects to gradually spiral towards each other and giving rise to shorter and shorter periods, was first propounded by Albert Einstein and later indirectly confirmed through the observation of the Hulse-Taylor binary. In general, great efforts have been made in order to understand what kinds of sources of gravitational waves the current detectors might be able to see. This happens because the sensitivity of the detectors depends on the accuracy with which waveforms can be predicted, so that they can be recognized against detector noise. In fact, the weak nature of gravitational radiation makes it very difficult to design a sensitive detector; filtering out the noisy background to isolate the useful signal requires great technical expertise, and is itself a field of research.

Fig. 6 - 3-D Rendering of gravitational waves originating from a binary compact object on course for collision.

Gravitational waves, whose emanation from a binary compact object merger is represented in Fig.6, are ripples in the spacetime which propagate in vacuum traveling along null directions, i.e. travel at the speed of light. Such results are determined within the approximation scheme of the linearized gravity, in which the metric tensor g is treated as a sum of the Minkowski metric η and a small perturbation h , such as

$$g_{\alpha\beta} = \eta_{\alpha\beta} + h_{\alpha\beta} \quad (3.50)$$

It can be verified that in absence of a stress-energy tensor, i.e. in the vacuum case, the Einstein field equations assume the form of the following D'Alembert

equation for the components of the perturbation metric.

$$\left(-\frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} + \nabla^2\right) \bar{h}^{\alpha\beta} = 0 \tag{3.51}$$

where $\bar{h}^{\alpha\beta}$ is representative of ten functions of the form

$$\bar{h}^{\alpha\beta} = A^{\alpha\beta} e^{ik_\alpha x^\alpha} \tag{3.52}$$

The action of gravitational waves is generally characterized as a stretching of space; as the wave passes through, the proper separations of free objects which are sitting at rest change with time. Such a stretching, however, is very difficult to measure, due to the order of magnitudes involved ($\sim 10^{-21}m$). In order to detect this very small perturbation, detectors have to operate in very large scales. Among the possible detection methods, only laser interferometers implemented in the LIGO observatory have succeeded in detecting gravitational waves. Basically these devices are Michelson interferometers, instruments invented in the 1880's, whose mirrors also serve as gravitational test masses. A passing gravitational wave will impress a phase modulation on the light in each arm of the interferometer, which can be detected and measured.

Fig. 7 - Basic Michelson interferometer with Fabry Perot cavities. The distance traveled by the beams is increased by mirrors placed near the beam splitter, which cause multiple reflections and keep the laser contained within the arms, greatly improving LIGO's sensitivity to changes in arm length like those caused by gravitational waves.

As shown in Fig. 7, the LIGO interferometer, whose “arms” are 4 km long, adds Fabry Perot cavities to the standard Michelson configuration: additional mirrors placed near the beam splitter are aligned in such a way that they reflect each laser beam back and forth along the entire length about 280 times before it finally merges with the beam which comes from the other arm. With such an improvement, the distance traveled by each laser beam increases from 4 km to 1120 km, enhancing LIGO’s sensitivity. Through the phase shifts in the interference pattern, the gravitational wave profile can then reconstructed and compared with theoretical “template” signals that would be produced by the different types and configurations of sources; in particular, signals may be referred to binary black holes, binary neutron stars or neutron star - black hole systems, of which properties such as the masses or the distance of the two objects can therefore be determined.

Chapter 4

The ADM formulation of Einstein's equations

4.1 Introduction

The Hamiltonian formulation, introduced at first in 1833 as a reformulation of classical mechanics by Rowan William Hamilton (1805-1865), is indeed a very general idea, later applied to different areas of physics. In 1962, Richard Arnowitt, Stanley Deser and Charles Misner determined, by applying an Hamiltonian approach to General Relativity, the ADM formulation of the same theory; such a formulation, commonly referred to also as 3+1 or Cauchy formulation, is actually a fundamental component of the modern theory of Relativity. The authors' theoretical approach has more interfaces with everyday life than the original formulation of Einstein's theory, and is also more suitable to computational implementations; the most intuitive concept is not, in fact, the one of a spacetime geometry, but that of a temporal succession of spatial geometries. It is thus interesting to think General Relativity as a "upside down built" theory, if compared to other physical theories, such as electromagnetism: as a matter of fact, in Maxwell's theory one starts with the well known concepts of electric charges, currents etc. and can eventually write down the more complex equation system presented below, which only later one realizes possessing a particular symmetry, the Lorentz transformation invariance.

$$\begin{cases} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{E} = \frac{\rho}{\epsilon_0} & (a) \\ \nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0 & (b) \\ \nabla \times \mathbf{E} = -\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} & (c) \\ \nabla \times \mathbf{B} = \mu_0 \mathbf{J} + \mu_0 \epsilon_0 \frac{\partial \mathbf{E}}{\partial t} & (d) \end{cases}$$

The four equations can be written in the more synthetic covariant form by introducing the following electromagnetic field tensor

$$F_{\mu\nu} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -E_j \\ E_i & F_{ij} \end{pmatrix} \quad (4.1)$$

with $F_{ij} = \epsilon_{ijk} H^k$, in which ϵ_{ijk} is the Levi-Civita symbol. Equations (a) and (d) can also be written as follows

$$\nabla_\nu F^{\mu\nu} = 4\pi J^\mu \quad (4.2)$$

with J^μ representing the current density four-vector; the remaining equations (b) and (c) can be written as

$$\nabla_\rho F_{\mu\nu} + \nabla_\mu F_{\nu\rho} + \nabla_\nu F_{\rho\mu} = 0 \quad (4.3)$$

The work that has to be done in the context of General Relativity is therefore to proceed in the “opposite direction”, starting from the selection of a specific time coordinate and the decomposition of each four-dimensional element in three-dimensional components and concluding with writing down the equations related to the translation of the manifestly covariant ones in terms of three-dimensional components. The final equations, under a coordinate transformation, will no longer be covariant, but, since the solution space remains unchanged, general coordinate transformations will still map solutions into solutions. The 3+1 decomposition of the four-dimensional spacetime starts with the choice of a synchronization, i.e. the foliation of the same in three-dimensional varieties in such a way that every point of the spacetime belongs to one and only one three-dimensional hypersurface. Time is then selected as a regular spacetime function such that the level hypersurfaces represent the desired foliation. In order to consider such a function ϕ as a local time coordinate, the resulting “slicing” of the spacetime has to be spacelike, namely:

$$g^{\mu\nu} \partial_\mu \phi \partial_\nu \phi < 0 \quad (4.4)$$

With such a choice made, the three-dimensional metric γ_{ij} on each leaf is induced by the four-dimensional spacetime metric $g_{\mu\nu}$. One then needs to establish a relationship between spatial coordinate systems x^i belonging to different leaves; such an operation can be carried out by choosing a congruence of time lines,

i.e. by requesting that points belonging to the same curve have the same spatial coordinates. In order to describe the curves, the following system is considered:

$$\frac{\partial x^\mu}{\partial \lambda} = \xi^\mu \quad (4.5)$$

with ξ being the tangent vector of the curve of properly chosen affine parameter λ , that is to verify

$$\xi^\mu \partial_\mu \phi = 1 \quad (4.6)$$

Therefore, by simply choosing

$$\xi_\mu = \partial_\mu \phi \quad (4.7)$$

the line element can be written as follows:

$$ds^2 = -\alpha^2 dt^2 + \gamma_{ij} dx^i dx^j \quad (4.8)$$

with α denoting the *lapse* function which relates the coordinate time t with the proper time τ ; it is, in other words, representative of the rate at which proper time is elapsed along the normal lines. It is to be noted that the lapse function can take different values, depending on the spacetime point in which it is evaluated, i.e. proper time elapsed when going from one to another leaf can vary from point to point, as represented in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8 - The same foliation is represented using local coordinate time t (left) and proper time τ (right). A particular lapse function has been chosen such that proper time evolution slows down in the central region, but remains uniform elsewhere (Bona, Palenzuela-Luque 2005).

Metric decomposition is analogous to decompose the electromagnetic tensor into its electric and magnetic field components; however, Einstein's field equations, contrary to Maxwell's, are of second order. Therefore, one also needs to decompose the first derivatives of the four-dimensional metric. In order to do this, it is convenient to refer to observers, named Eulerians, which are at rest with re-

spect to the spacetime synchronization. These observers move in spacetime in a direction which is orthogonal to all vectors confined to a spatial hypersurface; their four-velocity has components

$$u^\mu = \frac{1}{\alpha} \delta_0^\mu \quad (4.9)$$

and the tangent vector field points forward in time, i.e., from condition (4.6)

$$u^\mu = -n^\mu \quad (4.10)$$

with n^μ representing the normal vectors to the hypersurfaces. It can be proven [Ellis G.F.R., Van Helst H. 1998] that the motion of any observer can then be decomposed as follows

$$\nabla_\mu u_\nu = -u_\mu \dot{u}_\nu + \omega_{\mu\nu} + \chi_{\mu\nu} \quad (4.11)$$

$\dot{u}_\nu \equiv u^\rho \nabla_\rho u_\nu$ being the *four-acceleration*, the only non trivial projection of (4.11) along u^μ ; the antisymmetric tensor $\omega_{\mu\nu}$ represents the *vorticity*, while $\chi_{\mu\nu}$ is the symmetric *deformation* tensor. Eulerian observers have zero vorticity and four-acceleration given, according to (4.8), by

$$\dot{u}_\mu = (0, \partial_i \ln \alpha) \quad (4.12)$$

One can also notice, from this last expression, that the choice of a constant α corresponds to a free fall for Eulerian observers; therefore, the case just described is often regarded as “geodesic slicing”. The deformation tensor for Eulerian observers is described by

$$\chi_{\mu\nu} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -K_{ij} \end{pmatrix} \quad (4.13)$$

where the three-dimensional symmetric tensor K_{ij} denotes the extrinsic curvature of the slicing, having components

$$K_{ij} = -\frac{1}{2\alpha} \partial_t \gamma_{ij} \quad (4.14)$$

4.2 Decomposition of Einstein equations

Starting from the results described in the previous chapter, one can set Einstein's equations in the new form. In order to do this, Christoffel's symbols have to be computed at first; this last operation is not hard if one chooses to calculate the symbols using their representation in terms of the metric tensor components. It is then necessary, in order to write down the first member of the Einstein field equations, to calculate the components of the Ricci tensor. The decomposition of the source terms is the decomposition of the four-dimensional stress-energy tensor into the following *energy density*, *momentum density* and *stress tensor*:

$$\tau \equiv 8\pi T^{\mu\nu} n_\mu n_\nu \quad (4.15)$$

$$S_i \equiv 8\pi T_i^\mu n_\mu \quad (4.16)$$

$$S_{ij} \equiv 8\pi T_{ij} \quad (4.17)$$

It is also convenient to consider Einstein's equation in the following form:

$$\partial_\rho \Gamma_{\mu\nu}^\rho - \partial_\mu \Gamma_{\rho\nu}^\rho + \Gamma_{\mu\nu}^\lambda \Gamma_{\lambda\rho}^\rho - \Gamma_{\mu\lambda}^\rho \Gamma_{\rho\nu}^\lambda = 8\pi \left(T_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2} T g_{\mu\nu} \right) \quad (4.18)$$

where the relation $R = -8\pi T$ has been used, with R and T respectively representing the traces of the Ricci and the stress-energy tensor; also, the representation of the Ricci tensor as a function of the Christoffel symbols has been adopted. The $(0,0)$, $(0,i)$, and (i,j) component equations can be written as follows:

$$\frac{1}{\alpha} \partial_t \text{tr}(K) = -\frac{1}{\alpha} \delta\alpha + \text{tr}(K^2) + \frac{1}{2} (\text{tr}S + \tau) \quad (4.19)$$

$$0 = \nabla_j (K_i^j - \text{tr}K \delta_i^j) - S_i \quad (4.20)$$

$$\frac{1}{\alpha} \partial_t K_{ij} = -\frac{1}{\alpha} \nabla_i \nabla_j \alpha + R_{ij} - 2K_{ij}^2 + \text{tr}K K_{ij} - S_{ij} + \frac{1}{2} (\text{tr}S - \tau) \gamma_{ij} \quad (4.21)$$

and, by expliciting from (4.21) the term $\text{tr}K$ and substituting in (4.19), one obtains

$$0 = \text{tr}R + (\text{tr}K)^2 - \text{tr}(K^2) - 2\tau \quad (4.22)$$

As already mentioned before, the decomposition of equations (4.18) in (4.19), (4.20) and (4.21) has resulted in the loss of general covariance. However, a closer look to the right-hand-side terms of the equations shows that there still is a covariance, named 3+1, with respect to certain transformations; it can be noticed, in fact, that they show terms related to three-dimensional tensors, such as the Ricci tensor or the metric tensor, which are intrinsically defined by the geometry of the slices, or terms (such as the three-acceleration $\partial_t \ln \alpha$, the extrinsic curvature K_{ij} ,

and the different projections of the stress–energy tensor) which can be obtained from four-dimensional tensors by applying the elements n_μ , which are intrinsically given by the slicing. Therefore, in particular, the following transformations of spatial coordinates

$$y^i = F^i(x^j, t) \quad (4.23)$$

will preserve the geometry of every leaf, while time coordinate rescalings such as

$$t' = G(t) \quad (4.24)$$

will only interest the labeling of the slices, but not the slicing itself. It's interesting to notice what happens when applying transformation (4.23) to equation (4.19), whose right-hand side clearly acts as a 3+1 scalar. The first member of the equation then transforms as

$$\left(\frac{\partial \text{tr}K}{\partial t}\right)_{x=\text{const}} = \left(\frac{\partial \text{tr}K}{\partial t}\right)_{y=\text{const}} - \beta^k \left(\frac{\partial \text{tr}K}{\partial y^k}\right)_{t=\text{const}} \quad (4.25)$$

where β^k is the *shift* defined as follows:

$$\beta^k(y, t) \equiv \left(\frac{\partial y^k}{\partial x^r}\right) \left(\frac{\partial x^r}{\partial t}\right)_{y=\text{const}} \quad (4.26)$$

Furthermore, it is important to notice that the lapse function transforms under (4.24) as

$$\alpha' = \alpha \left(\frac{\partial t}{\partial t'}\right) \quad (4.27)$$

so it is not a 3+1 scalar, while the element

$$\frac{1}{\alpha} \partial_t \quad (4.28)$$

is preserved under the same transformation. A more general form, covariant under 3+1 transformations, can then be found for the left-hand side of (4.19), reformulating as follows

$$\frac{1}{\alpha} (\partial_t - \beta^k \partial_k) \text{tr}K \quad (4.29)$$

and the factor in parentheses can be rewritten as

$$(\partial_t - \mathcal{L}_\beta) \quad (4.30)$$

It is eventually possible to write down Einstein's field equations for a generic coordinate system in the following form, which is often referred to as the ADM formulation, named for its authors Richard Arnowitt, Stanley Deser and Charles

W. Misner:

$$\frac{1}{\alpha}(\partial_t - \mathcal{L}_\beta)\gamma_{ij} = -2K_{ij} \quad (4.31)$$

$$\frac{1}{\alpha}(\partial_t - \mathcal{L}_\beta)K_{ij} = -\frac{1}{\alpha}\nabla_i\nabla_j\alpha + R_{ij} - 2K_{ij}^2 + \text{tr}KK_{ij} - S_{ij} + \frac{1}{2}(\text{tr}S - \tau)\gamma_{ij} \quad (4.32)$$

$$0 = \nabla_j(K_i^j - \text{tr}K\delta_i^j) - S_i \quad (4.33)$$

$$0 = \text{tr}R + (\text{tr}K)^2 - \text{tr}(K^2) - 2\tau \quad (4.34)$$

It is also possible to generalize the line element, by considering the application of (4.23) to the same, to the non-zero shift case, obtaining

$$ds^2 = -\alpha^2 dt^2 + \gamma_{ij}(dy^i + \beta^i dt)(dy^j + \beta^j dt) \quad (4.35)$$

Before discussing the equation system in more detail, some remarkable considerations about the presence of a shift vector have to be done. Indeed, a non zero-shift results in formal complications already found in the computation of the components of the inverse matrix of the four-dimensional metric, and then in the structure of the Christoffel symbols, which contain now much more terms. However, there are physical situations in which a non-zero shift can be convenient: it is the case, for example, of the study of a system in which rotation is a not negligible characteristic (a spinning black hole, or a binary system); one can then choose a co-rotating coordinate system and, in order to adapt time lines to rotate with the bodies, a non-zero shift must be introduced. In the process of analyzing the ADM equations, it is immediate to notice that the temporal evolution of the γ_{ij} and K_{ij} fields is ruled by equations (4.31) and (4.32); the last one, corresponding to the spatial components of the four-dimensional Ricci tensor, together with (4.31), constitutes the ‘‘Ricci evolution system’’. By substituting (4.34) in (4.32), in order to eliminate the presence of the energy density τ , one determines

$$(\partial_t - \mathcal{L}_\beta)K_{ij} = -\nabla_i\nabla_j\alpha + \alpha[R_{ij} - 2K_{ij}^2 + \text{tr}KK_{ij} - S_{ij}] - \frac{\alpha}{4}[\text{tr}R + (\text{tr}K)^2 - \text{tr}(K^2) - 2\text{tr}S]\gamma_{ij} \quad (4.36)$$

This last equation, together with (4.31), constitutes the ‘‘Einstein evolution system’’, because it can be obtained from the components of the four-dimensional Einstein tensor. Equations (4.33) and (4.34), in which no time derivatives of K_{ij} are present, can be considered constraining for the energy ϵ and the momentum M_i , defined as follows

$$\epsilon \equiv \frac{1}{2}[\text{tr}R + (\text{tr}K)^2 - \text{tr}(K^2)] - \tau = 0 \quad (4.37)$$

$$M_i \equiv \nabla_j(K_i^j - \text{tr}K\delta_i^j) - S_i = 0 \quad (4.38)$$

Although the Ricci and the Einstein systems are not equivalent, the complete set formed by any of them together with the energy and momentum constraints is the same one, having only combined the same equations in different ways.

In the light of the above considerations, a strong similarity with the initially introduced covariant Maxwell equations emerges: in that case, the time evolution of the fields (electric \mathbf{E} and magnetic \mathbf{B}) is also governed by only two of the four equations. Equations (a) and (b) can be considered then as constraints and one can also show, using electric charge continuity equation and equations (c) and (d), that time evolution does not introduce others, which is equivalent to say that the constraints are preserved in time. For the Einstein field equations, given the conservation laws from the study of the system written in the “standard” form (3.29), it is possible to verify that equations (4.37) and (4.38) represent the first integrals relatively to time evolution equations (4.32) and (4.31); the strong similarity with Maxwell’s equations is again found.

4.3 Significant applications of the ADM formulation

The ADM formulation has an important application in modern Numerical Relativity, a General Relativity field which uses numerical methods and algorithms to analyze and solve its problems. The general procedure in order to execute computational algorithms which apply the ADM theory essentially involves the initial specification of the metric for the object which has to be studied and the foliation characteristic parameters (the lapse function α and the extrinsic curvature K). Equations (4.37) and (4.38), first integrals of the evolution system, can be implemented as initial or boundary conditions; sometimes they can also be employed as qualitative controls of calculations. Then, the determination of the physical quantities of interest happens with the temporal evolution of the K_{ij} and γ_{ij} parameters through the evolution equations; this procedure, which is generally applied with the finite difference method, is often referred to as Free Evolution and is the most used in the Numerical Relativity field for a long time (its first application was made by Smarr in 1979).

Significant applications, dating back to '90s, have been the ones referred to nude singularities (Shapiro and Teukolsky, 1991) or to the discovery of a critical behavior in black hole formation (Choptuik, 1993). However, in the attempt of running long-term simulations, regarding, for example, the coalescence of binary neutron star systems or binary black hole systems in order to calculate the form of outgoing gravitational waves, these often fail because of the appearing of divergences in the iteration cycle. With the suspicion that the manifestation of the differences was attributable to the specific formulation of the equations, various formulations of modified ADM have been introduced: the most important and used is the Baumgarte-Shapiro-Shibata-Nakamura (BSSN formulation) one, in which, instead of considering the evolution of K_{ij} and γ_{ij} , new parameters, defined starting from the latter, are considered. BSSN equations remain stable in long-term simulation, although the reason of this is not entirely clear.

Furthermore, the ADM Hamiltonian formulation has contributed to the attempts made in order to construct a quantum gravity theory. In particular, this corresponds to the "Canonical Quantum Gravity" research line, i.e. the attempts, principally carried forward by Dirac, Peres and Bergmann et al. as well as Arnowitt, Deser and Misner. They seek to construct a theory in which the Hilbert space contains a representation of the metric or some of the metric functions; in the '60s Wheeler and DeWitt determined the formal equations of the theory, although inadequately defined. The well-defined versions of the same equations were determined only in the '80s, with loop quantum gravity.

Chapter 5

Numerical Methods

5.1 Finite Difference Approximation

The need of finite-difference approximation (FDA) of a partial differential equation (PDE) arises when one has to solve it through a computer. The essence of FDA is the replacement of the continuum with a discrete lattice of points, the *grid*, and the substitution of differential operators with appropriate expressions which involve the function value in different grid points. These expressions can be easily deduced using a Taylor expansion. For example, one can consider the approximation of the first spatial derivative of a function $u(x, t)$ which depends both on space and time; such a derivative can be denoted as $u_x(x, t)$.

If $\Delta x = h$ for further simplifying the notation, the function values in three points $j - 1, j, j + 1$ are obtained, up to the third order of Taylor expansion, according to the following equations

$$u_{j-1} = u_j - h(u_x)_j + \frac{1}{2}h^2(u_{xx})_j + O(h^3) \quad (5.1)$$

$$u_j = u_j \quad (5.2)$$

$$u_{j+1} = u_j + h(u_x)_j + \frac{1}{2}h^2(u_{xx})_j + O(h^3) \quad (5.3)$$

One can now seek for a linear combination of u_{j-1} , u_j and u_{j+1} which results in $(u_x)_j$ with $O(h^2)$ accuracy:

$$c_-u_{j-1} + c_0u_j + c_+u_{j+1} = (u_x)_j + O(h^2) \quad (5.4)$$

Fig. 9 - Portion of uniform finite-difference grid; the spacings in both the spatial and temporal directions are constant, although in general they are not equal (Choptuik 1999).

In order to determine the three coefficients c_- , c_0 and c_+ , the system of the following three equations has to be solved

$$c_- + c_0 + c_+ = 0 \quad (5.5)$$

$$-hc_- + hc_+ = 1 \quad (5.6)$$

$$\frac{1}{2}h^2c_- + \frac{1}{2}h^2c_+ = 0 \quad (5.7)$$

The solution yields

$$c_- = -\frac{1}{2h} \quad (5.8)$$

$$c_0 = 0 \quad (5.9)$$

$$c_+ = \frac{1}{2h} \quad (5.10)$$

Equation (5.4) now reads

$$\frac{u(x+h) - u(x-h)}{2h} = (u_x)_j + O(h^2) \quad (5.11)$$

The same technique can also be used in order to calculate higher order derivatives. All the calculations are done with a specific, finite value of h : this represents the basic control parameter of the FDA. In fact, one is interested in the way the discrete solution varies in function of h and, in particular, in the “continuum limit”, i.e. as the grid spacing approaches 0.

5.2 A simple discretization: 1D wave equation

An immediate application of the Finite Difference Method has been carried out in the context of this thesis work as an initial training on numerical methods. The first step of this operation has regarded the solution to the problem of the one-dimensional wave equation with initial and periodic boundary conditions within the spatial domain $0 \leq x \leq 1$ and the temporal domain $t \geq 0$, which is described by the following equations:

$$u_{tt} = u_{xx} \quad (5.12)$$

$$u(x, 0) = u_0(x) \quad (5.13)$$

$$u_t(x, 0) = g_0(x) \quad (5.14)$$

$$u(0, t) = u(1, t) \quad (5.15)$$

The first equation is D'Alembert's formula $u_{tt} = c^2 u_{xx}$ with the simplification $c = 1$ for the propagation speed of the wave; equations (5.13) and (5.14) respectively explicit the initial values of the function and of its time derivative, while equation (5.15) represents the periodicity of the function at the boundaries. As already discussed in the previous paragraph, the first discretization step is represented by the creation of a grid of points; still referring to Fig.9, the following notation can be introduced:

$$t^n \equiv n\Delta t, \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots \quad (5.16)$$

$$x_j \equiv j\Delta x, \quad j = 0, 1, 2, \dots, J \quad (5.17)$$

$$u_j^n \equiv u(j\Delta x, n\Delta t) \quad (5.18)$$

$$\Delta x = \frac{1}{J} = h \quad (5.19)$$

$$\lambda = \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta x} \quad (5.20)$$

where the Courant number λ is chosen < 1 and the time discretization scale is determined consequently with (5.20). Equation (5.12) can be written down as follows using the finite difference representation

$$\frac{u_j^{n+1} - 2u_j^n + u_j^{n-1}}{\Delta t^2} = \frac{u_{j+1}^n - 2u_j^n + u_{j-1}^n}{\Delta x^2} \quad (5.21)$$

Equations (5.13) and (5.14) refer to the first two time levels of data, i.e. one has to specify u_j^0 and u_j^1 , with $j = 0, 1, \dots, J$; in particular, they have to be chosen ensuring that (5.12) and (5.14) are respected. In this sense, the simple choice

implemented in the code has been

$$u(x, t) = \sin(x - t) \quad (5.22)$$

therefore, the values for u_j^0 and u_j^1 are determined to be

$$u_j^0 = \sin(j\Delta x) \quad (5.23)$$

$$u_j^1 = -\cos(j\Delta x) \quad (5.24)$$

On the other hand, equation (5.15) simply translates in

$$u_0^n = u_j^n = k^n \quad (5.25)$$

where k^n is a value which depends on the particular n -th time level. In order to solve equation (5.21) for $j = 1, 2, \dots, J - 1$, and for all the time levels from $n = 2$ on, one can explicit in the following form

$$u_j^{n+1} = 2u_j^n - u_j^{n-1} + (u_{j+1}^n - 2u_j^n + u_{j-1}^n) \quad (5.26)$$

The case $j = 0$ has to be treated apart, as there is no $j = -1$ level; with periodic boundary conditions being present, however, this abstract spatial level corresponds to the $J - 1$ one, so (5.26) becomes

$$u_0^{n+1} = 2u_0^n - u_0^{n-1} + (u_1^n - 2u_0^n + u_{J-1}^n) \quad (5.27)$$

One can also observe that the point labeled with $j = J$ does not represent a problem, as the value of the function in that point is simply u_0^n and can be copied directly. After the computation of the solution, the second step has regarded the treatment of the convergence problem. In general, in fact, the computed solution differs from the exact solution and an evaluation of this difference has to be done. The key to this analysis is L.F. Richardson's observation [Richardson L.F., 1910], that the solution u^h of a FDA with scale parameter h has the following expansion in the limit $h \rightarrow 0$:

$$u^h(x, t) = u(x, t) + h^2 e_2(x, t) + h^4 e_4(x, t) + \dots \quad (5.28)$$

where $u(x, t)$ represents the continuum solution, and e_2, e_4 , etc. are error functions which do not depend on h . This fact can be used in order to elaborate a simple convergence test; the requirement is the computation of three distinct solutions u^h, u^{2h}, u^{4h} of the same problem (i.e. the same wave equation with equal initial and boundary constraints) at the respective resolutions $h, 2h, 4h$. Another assumption that has to be made is that the grids can be thought as

“superposed”, i.e. the $4h$ grid points represent a subset of the $2h$ grid points, which also are a subset of the h points, so the values the function assumes at the common points can be easily compared one to another without requiring interpolation. Applications of equation (5.28) to the three distinct solutions can then be written down:

$$u^h = u + h^2 e_2 + h^4 e_4 + \dots \quad (5.29)$$

$$u^{2h} = u + (2h)^2 e_2 + (2h)^4 e_4 + \dots \quad (5.30)$$

$$u^{4h} = u + (4h)^2 e_2 + (4h)^4 e_4 + \dots \quad (5.31)$$

The convergence factor Q , defined as follow, can now be computed

$$Q = \frac{\|u^{4h} - u^{2h}\|_2}{\|u^{2h} - u^h\|_2} \quad (5.32)$$

where the subtractions are performed considering the common points between the $4h$ and $2h$, as well as the $2h$ and h grids; the symbol $\|\cdot\|_2$ refers to the l_2 norm

$$\|u^h\|_2 = \left[(J+1)^{-1} \sum_{j=0}^J (u_j^h)^2 \right]^{1/2} \quad (5.33)$$

It can be proven that, if the considered finite difference scheme is converging, then the following condition is verified

$$\lim_{h \rightarrow 0} Q = 4 \quad (5.34)$$

In order to monitor the convergence level over the temporal evolution, the Q factor should be computed for every time “line”. In addition to this “global” convergence test, a local one can also be performed by considering the calculation of the Q factor for a single common point, i.e.

$$Q = \frac{u^{4h} - u^{2h}}{u^{2h} - u^h} \quad (5.35)$$

again, as expected, convergence is achieved if (5.34) is verified. The entire code of the developed program, which has been written in C language, is reported in Appendix A; although the global Richardson test is currently enabled, the program allows both local and global Richardson tests.

5.3 The Conformal Thin Sandwich formulation

The principal purpose of numerical relativity is to use numerical methods and algorithms in order to study spacetimes that cannot be studied by analytic means. Numerical relativity has been applied in many areas: cosmological models, perturbed black holes and neutron stars, the coalescence of black holes and neutron stars, etc. In any of these cases, Einstein's equations can be formulated in several ways in order to evolve the dynamics. All of these methods start with setting the fields on some hypersurface, representing the initial data, and then evolve these data to neighboring hypersurfaces. The decomposition which has been chosen in the context of this thesis work is the Conformal Thin Sandwich, which considers the evolution of the metric between two neighboring hypersurfaces (the thin sandwich). The starting point is represented by the four constraint equations (4.37) and (4.38) and the following conformal decomposition of the three-dimensional metric γ_{ij} , i.e. the spatial metric is written as a product of some power of a positive scaling factor (the *conformal factor*) ψ and an auxiliary 3-metric $\tilde{\gamma}_{ij}$ (the *conformally related metric*)

$$\gamma_{ij} = \psi^4 \tilde{\gamma}_{ij} \quad (5.36)$$

Evolution equation (4.31) is then used to connect the 3-metrics on the two neighboring surfaces, which can be labeled with times t and t' , where

$$t' = t + \delta t \quad (5.37)$$

and

$$\gamma'_{ij} = \gamma_{ij} + (\partial_t \gamma_{ij}) \delta t \quad (5.38)$$

The following definitions are now made

$$u_{ij} \equiv \gamma^{1/3} \partial_t (\gamma^{-1/3} \gamma_{ij}) \quad (5.39)$$

$$\tilde{u}_{ij} \equiv \partial_t \tilde{\gamma}_{ij} \quad (5.40)$$

$$\tilde{\gamma}^{ij} \tilde{u}_{ij} \equiv 0 \quad (5.41)$$

where, in particular, in (5.39), u_{ij} is defined as the traceless part of the time derivative of the spatial metric. Equations (5.40) and (5.41) are both used to uniquely determine the conformal scaling of u_{ij} , represented by

$$u_{ij} = \psi^4 \tilde{u}_{ij} \quad (5.42)$$

It is now convenient to split K_{ij} into its trace K and a traceless part A_{ij} as showed in

$$K_{ij} = A_{ij} + \frac{1}{3}\gamma_{ij}K \quad (5.43)$$

where A_{ij} and K conformally transform separately, respectively according to

$$A^{ij} = \psi^\alpha \tilde{A}^{ij} \quad (5.44)$$

$$K = \psi^\beta \tilde{K} \quad (5.45)$$

where the two exponents α and β are still undetermined. It can be proven that the divergence of any symmetric, traceless tensor A_{ij} which transforms according to (5.44) satisfies

$$D_j A^{ij} = \psi^{-10} \tilde{D}_j (\psi^{10+\alpha} \tilde{A}^{ij}) \quad (5.46)$$

So the natural choice $\alpha = -10$ can be applied, so that the tensor A^{ij} transforms as follows

$$A^{ij} = \psi^{-10} \tilde{A}^{ij} \quad (5.47)$$

Treating K as a conformal invariant, i.e. $K = \tilde{K}$ and $\beta = 0$, equations (4.37) and (4.38) related to the Hamiltonian and momentum constraint can be written down in the new form, yielding respectively

$$8\tilde{D}^2\psi - \psi\tilde{R} - \frac{2}{3}\psi^5 K^2 + \psi^{-7}\tilde{A}_{ij}\tilde{A}^{ij} = -16\pi\psi^5\rho \quad (5.48)$$

and

$$\tilde{D}_j \tilde{A}^{ij} - \frac{2}{3}\psi^6 \tilde{\gamma}^{ij} \tilde{D}_j K = 8\pi\psi^{10} S^i \quad (5.49)$$

where the new ρ and S^i are equal to the ‘‘old’’ τ and S^i used in eq. (4.37) and (4.38) divided by a factor 8π . According to equations (5.39) and (5.43), equation (4.31) can be rewritten in the following form

$$u^{ij} = -2\alpha A^{ij} + (L\beta)^{ij} \quad (5.50)$$

where

$$(L\beta)^{ij} = D^i \beta^j + D^j \beta^i - \frac{2}{3}\delta^{ij} D_k \beta^k \quad (5.51)$$

Moreover, it can be proven that

$$(L\beta)^{ij} = \psi^{-4} (\tilde{L}\beta)^{ij} \quad (5.52)$$

From equations (5.42), (5.47) and (5.51), equation (5.50) can be conformally transformed in

$$\tilde{A}^{ij} = \frac{\psi^6}{2\alpha} [(\tilde{L}\beta)^{ij} - \tilde{u}^{ij}] \quad (5.53)$$

which can be simplified by introducing the conformally rescaled lapse $\tilde{\alpha}$ according to

$$\alpha = \psi^6 \tilde{\alpha} \quad (5.54)$$

and becoming

$$\tilde{A}^{ij} = \frac{1}{2\tilde{\alpha}} [(\tilde{L}\beta)^{ij} - \tilde{u}^{ij}] \quad (5.55)$$

Inserting the last results into the momentum constraint equation, (5.49) can be rewritten as follows

$$(\tilde{\Delta}_L \beta)^i - (\tilde{L}\beta)^{ij} \tilde{D}_j \ln(\tilde{\alpha}) = \tilde{\alpha} \tilde{D}_j (\tilde{\alpha}^{-1} \tilde{u}^{ij}) + \frac{4}{3} \tilde{\alpha} \psi^6 \tilde{D}^i K + 16\pi \tilde{\alpha} \psi^{10} S^i \quad (5.56)$$

where the Laplacian $(\tilde{\Delta}_L \beta)^i = \tilde{D}^2 \beta^i + \frac{1}{3} \tilde{D}^i \tilde{D}_j \beta^j$. The Hamiltonian constraint, represented by eq. (4.34), acquires the new form

$$\tilde{D}^2 \psi - \frac{1}{8} \psi \tilde{R} - \frac{1}{12} \psi^5 K^2 + \frac{1}{8} \psi^{-7} \tilde{A}_{ij} \tilde{A}^{ij} = -2\pi \psi^5 \rho \quad (5.57)$$

The particular hypotheses applied in the context of this thesis work and the complete expression of the equations are reported in Appendix B.

5.4 The multigrid Gauss-Seidel method

The solution of partial differential equations is an important topic that appears in different areas of physics (e.g. in quantum mechanics, fluid dynamics, heat transfer, etc.). Both analytic and numerical solutions for these problems do exist; analytic solutions, which are often very difficult to find, if not impossible, find a function that satisfies the PDE with the given initial and boundary conditions. Since most of PDEs cannot be solved analytically, numerical methods have to be implemented in order to solve the problem; computers are then used to get approximate numerical solutions.

Elliptic PDEs, in particular, can be solved with a variety of methods; however, a general approach is represented by relaxation methods, whose basic idea is to transform an elliptic equation of the form

$$Lf = 0 \tag{5.58}$$

into a parabolic equation such as

$$\dot{f} = Lf \tag{5.59}$$

in which the dot denotes a time derivation. If the latter equation admits stationary solutions, the same solutions will be valid also for the initial equation. So, in general, one begins with choosing an initial guess for f and solves the initial value problem; then, with time evolution, the solution can end up to a stationary state within a certain acceptance interval, or rather diverges. A useful quantity to define in this context is the following *residual* r

$$r \equiv -Lf \tag{5.60}$$

in fact, if f^* is an exact solution of eq. (5.58), then its residual will be zero, and so it will also be for the left-hand side of equation (5.59). Otherwise, the relaxation process will act on the function f according to the following expression

$$\dot{f} = -r \tag{5.61}$$

which also explains the fact that the convergence slows down when getting closer to the solution, as the residual decreases. One can also define a *solution error* e , for every step of the iteration, as the difference between a solution f^* and a given iterate f :

$$e \equiv f^* - f \tag{5.62}$$

Multigrid solvers based on relaxation methods improve the convergence speed

by implementing a hierarchy of grids, in which the coarser ones cover a subset of the points that belong to the finer grids. Of course, finest grids should be implemented in correspondence of the areas which are of physical interest and should be solved at maximum resolution (e.g. in correspondence of the two neutron stars constituting a binary system). Since, as already showed, the relaxation speed is higher in points in which the residual is higher but decreases as one approaches the solution, one could stop the process as soon as the error reaches a plateau, and start solving for e directly. The equation which e has to satisfy, which can be derived starting from the previous definitions, is the following

$$L(f + e) - L(f) = r \quad (5.63)$$

Therefore, the strategy is to relax this equation until the convergence speed slows down, and then begin relaxing the error of e and so on. The particular relaxation scheme implemented in the CT_MULTILEVEL solver is a standard Gauss-Seidel method which can be considered as a variation of the Jacobi method. A simple way to introduce the latter is represented by the following example:

$$u_j^{n+1} - 2u_j^n + u_j^{n-1} = h^2 f_j \quad 1 \leq j \leq n - 1 \quad (5.64)$$

with also

$$u_0 = u_n = 0 \quad (5.65)$$

in which the notation used is the same of the previous chapters, where f_j represents the known term of the equation. It is also useful to express equation (5.64) in the following matrix notation

$$Au = f \quad (5.66)$$

where A is the coefficient matrix, which, in this specific case, consists of just one row; using the same formalism, eq. (5.63) reads

$$Ae = r \quad (5.67)$$

The scheme consists in the following procedure: one solves the j th equation of (5.64) for the j th unknown, using the current approximation for the $(j - 1)$ th and $(j + 1)$ th unknowns. When applied to the vector of current approximations, this produces an iteration scheme that can be written as

$$v_j^{(1)} = \frac{1}{2}(v_j^{(0)} + v_j^{(0)} + h^2 f_j) \quad (5.68)$$

where $v^{(0)}$ represents the current approximation, while $v^{(1)}$ denotes the new so-

lution. When all the vector components are updated, the process repeats until convergence is achieved. The Gauss-Seidel method adds the fact that the new components are used as soon as they are computed; therefore, eq. (5.68) may be written using the following notation

$$v_j \leftarrow \frac{1}{2}(v_{j-1} + v_{j+1} + h^2 f_j) \quad (5.69)$$

where the arrow represents the replacement operation. It is also useful to express the method in the more general matrix form, initially referring to eq. (5.66). It is possible to split the matrix A in the following form

$$A = D - L - U \quad (5.70)$$

where D is the main diagonal of A and $-L$ and $-U$ represent the strictly lower and upper triangular parts of the same matrix, respectively. By substituting in eq. (5.66), one obtains

$$(D - L - U)u = f \quad (5.71)$$

In this last expression, the three terms can be splitted as follows, resulting in the new form

$$(D - L)u = Uu + f \quad (5.72)$$

If one left-multiplies by $(D - L)^{-1}$, the equation reads

$$u = (D - L)^{-1}Uu + (D - L)^{-1}f \quad (5.73)$$

Defining the Gauss-Seidel iteration matrix as

$$R_G = (D - L)^{-1}U \quad (5.74)$$

the method can be expressed as follows

$$v \leftarrow R_G v + (D - L)^{-1}f \quad (5.75)$$

As a final remark on the method, it is important to notice that the order of updating is significant; one can sweep through the components in ascending or descending order, or also alternate between ascending and descending orders.

The Gauss-Seidel method, as many other standard iterative methods, possesses the smoothing property, which makes these methods very effective at eliminating the high-frequency or oscillatory components of the error, while leaving the low-frequency or smooth components relatively unchanged. Therefore, multi-grid techniques have to be implemented in order to make the method effective on all error components. The particular approach used by the CT_MULTILEVEL

consists of the full multigrid V-cycle (FMG) scheme represented in Fig. 10.

Fig. 10 - Schedule of grids for a V-cycle (a) and FMG scheme (b).

Before discussing into more detail the FMG scheme, the single V-cycle scheme, also presented in Fig.10, has to be discussed as it is continuously applied to the former. The algorithm, which is now described schematically, starts from the finest grid, exploring all the grids (labeled with $h, 2h, \dots, Nh$) and eventually reaching the coarsest one:

- Relax on $A^h u^h = f^h$ n_1 times with initial guess v^h .
- Compute $f^{2h} = I_h^{2h} r^h$.
- Relax on $A^{2h} u^{2h} = f^{2h}$ n_1 times with initial guess $v^{2h} = 0$.
- Compute $f^{4h} = I_{2h}^{4h} r^{2h}$.
- Continue until reaching the coarsest grid, where just solve $A^{Nh} u^{Nh} = f^{Nh}$.

- Correct $v^{(N/2)h} \leftarrow v^{(N/2)h} + I_{Nh}^{(N/2)h} v^{Nh}$.
- Relax on $A^{(N/2)h} u^{(N/2)h} = f^{(N/2)h}$ n_2 times with initial guess $v^{(N/2)h}$.
- Continue until reaching the finest grid.

The two operators I_{nh}^{2nh} and I_{2nh}^h act as restriction and prolongation operators, respectively. The entire procedure, summarized with $v^h \leftarrow V^h(v^h, f^h)$ is now applied to the FMG scheme as follows:

- Initialize $f^{2h} \leftarrow I_h^{2h} f^h$, $f^{4h} \leftarrow I_{2h}^{4h} f^{2h}$, ...
- Solve or relax on the coarsest grid.
- $v^{(N/2)h} \leftarrow I_{Nh}^{(N/2)h} v^{Nh}$
- $v^{(N/2)h} \leftarrow V^{(N/2)h}(v^{(N/2)h}, f^{(N/2)h})$ m times.
- Proceed until:
- $v^h \leftarrow I_{2h}^h v^{2h}$
- $v^h \leftarrow V^h(v^h, f^h)$ m times.

Chapter 6

The initial data construction

6.1 Project plan

The process of production of accurate initial data for binary neutron stars can be structured in a number of tasks to be fulfilled. It is remarkable the fact that to date, very few public programs able to construct these initial data exist, the most important of which is the public software LORENE, which uses spectral methods for the purpose.

The first step requires the determination of a realistic initial guess to be used as starting point of the iteration process. Said initial guess comes from the TOVSTAR program, which, as it will be better discussed later, solves the TOV equation with a given central rest mass density and equation of state, i.e. it can model a single neutron star. In principle, this represents an exact solution of the Einstein field equations in the continuum limit; when a discretization of the domain is introduced, however, a small error is also added. The latter can be estimated by computing the violation of the Hamiltonian constraint (4.37), i.e. the quantity which represents how much the Hamiltonian constraint differs from 0 (which is representative of the analytic solution): in fact, as the star hasn't got any velocity, nor the time evolution is activated, this is the only Einstein field equation "enabled".

The second step involves the construction of the binary system: TOVSTAR, and, consequently the PIZZATO implementation of the program which has been used, in fact, cannot create a superposition of TOV solutions in its original state and modifications to the same are necessary. These modifications, which are later discussed, have been carried out by me and have been consequently implemented in the code. Modifications to the original program have also been made in order

to add a velocity to the neutron stars; at this point, with the superposition and the velocities enabled, the initial guess is not a solution of the Einstein's equations anymore, and the Hamiltonian constraint violation has become higher. In addition, the velocity introduction also determines violations for the three momentum constraints (4.38) which now are not identically satisfied.

The third step is related to the application of the `CT_MULTILEVEL` solver to the previously constructed initial guess, in order to lower the constraint violations; in particular, the solver acts applying an FMG cycle in order to iteratively solve the constraint equations in the Conformal Thin Sandwich form (which are included in Appendix B), lowering the violation peaks and tending to make the global constraint violation homogeneous.

The most noteworthy results are then represented by the constraint violations, which is important to compute before and after the solver activation, in order to evaluate its action.

6.2 Computational setup

In order to construct initial data for binary neutron stars, Einstein’s equations have to be solved in a discretized spacetime: the Einstein Toolkit software, and, in particular, the CT_MULTILEVEL solver has been used for this purpose; the software is a collection of over one hundred modules which primarily belong to the Cactus infrastructure. The latter is constituted by a central component, the “*flesh*” which coordinates a number of peripheral modules, the “*thorns*” which have, in general, different functions, ranging from the capability of constructing and managing a grid or a set of grids (e.g. the thorn CARPET), to the possibility of solving equations or set of equations (e.g. the thorn used in the context of this thesis work, CT_MULTILEVEL). In particular, the set of modules which also belong to the Einstein Toolkit are mainly used in the contexts of cosmology and relativistic astrophysics. The organization in modules which can be activated when needed makes the infrastructure very flexible; it is also possible to “convert” codes in Cactus modules, as it has been done for the TOVSTAR program, which will be discussed in detail in the next section.

Important considerations have to be done on the particular setups which one can use in order to implement the single neutron star or the binary system: too large spacings between the grid points, for example, can lead to under-resolutions which, in turn, can result in divergences, while too little spacings introduce too many points and equations to be solved, raising the computational cost of the simulation. The CT_MULTILEVEL solver also adds a variety of parameters which have to be considered and set carefully, such as the number of iterations to do on each level.

It follows then that the production of very accurate initial data requires a great amount of computing power. While simple test setups involving few iterations of the solver on a small set of grid points require a few GB of RAM and may be run also on personal computers, increasing the number of iterations or points also forces to work on more powerful and complex infrastructures, as simulations can require up to 1 TB of RAM.

The new Cineca supercomputer ‘MARCONI’ has been used for the purpose: it represents the new Italian class Tier-0 supercomputer, and is available to the scientific community since June 2016. The system is based on the recently announced Intel® Xeon® E5-2697 v4 processor, based on Intel’s x86 architecture, and is designed to reach a computational power of 2 Pflops; moreover, in the near future, the infrastructure is planned to reach a total computational power of about 20Pflop/s utilizing future generation Intel Xeon processors. Actually, the supercomputer consists of 1.512 nodes, each constituted by 36 cores, so 54.432 cores in total are present; 3.5 GB of RAM are provided by each core, so that an

entire node allows the use of 128 GB of RAM.

The system has allowed the modeling of binary neutron stars in large grids and the possibility to add both other global and local grids with minor spacings. The implementation of the binary system in large grids is fundamental: during time evolution, in fact, the gravitational waveform has to be evaluated at a very large distance (infinite in the ideal limit) from the stars. The introduction of local grids is also a factor of great importance; it allows, in fact, a better resolution only in the interesting regions, e.g. in correspondence of the neutron stars, and, at the same time, doesn't increase the computing power required dramatically.

6.3 Solving the TOV equation

Actually, a number of solutions, both private and public, exists in order to generate initial data for binary neutron stars. The TOVSTAR program, authored by Dr. Wolfgang Kastaun, is a private program which can be executed within the Einstein Toolkit; the program is used to compute TOV solutions for arbitrary polytropic equations of state (EOS). The input is represented by a file containing the name of the file specifying which EOS has to be used and the central rest mass density (*rmc.c*) of the object, e.g.

```
eos      = EOS_BU
rmc_c    = 7.9056 e+17
```

where the file *EOS_BU* has the following form:

```
name     = BU (Polytropic)
type     = polytrope
poly_n   = 1
poly_rmc = 6.176 e+18
```

where two different types can be specified for the EOS, either polytrope or tabulated. Assuming a polytrope EOS, the polytropic index n (*poly-n*), related to the polytropic exponent Γ through $\Gamma = 1 + 1/n$ needs to be specified, as well as the polytropic density scale ρ_p (*poly-rmc*) which can be specified instead of the usual polytropic constant by considering eq. (3.43) in the form

$$P = \rho_p \left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_p} \right)^\Gamma \quad (6.1)$$

The program solves the TOV equation for an ideal non-rotating fluid and may subsequently consider a slow rotation by computing rotational corrections up to first order. This slow rotation approximation only yields a frame dragging coefficient $\bar{\omega}$, apart from that the solution is the same as for the non-rotating case. The line element becomes

$$ds^2 = -e^{2\Phi} dt^2 + e^{2\lambda} dr^2 + r^2 d\theta^2 + r^2 \sin^2 \theta (d\phi^2 - 2\omega d\phi dt) \quad (6.2)$$

with

$$\bar{\omega} = \Omega - \omega \quad (6.3)$$

Where Ω denotes the angular velocity seen by a distant observer.

As already stated, the program is used in order to 'model' a neutron star, which translates in the definition, for every point of the grid, of the hydrodynamic and geometric variables. Therefore, the program outputs various text files, two of which are particularly important. The first one collects the "Star model

parameters”, i.e. the parameters, expressed in MKS units, related to the star as a whole, such as the mass, the radius, the compactness etc. The second file comprises all the geometric and hydrodynamic variables varying as a function of the radius. The program can transfer the results within the Einstein Toolkit through the implementation as a Cactus module, under the name PIZZATOV, which has been carried out by Dr. Kastaun as well. In this case, results are not directly output as before, but are rather stored in other Cactus modules; in particular, the geometric variables are stored in ADMBase, while the hydrodynamic variables are stored in HydroBase. As, in its standard configuration, the program can solve the TOV for the modeling of a single neutron star, changes are needed in order to construct the binary system; in particular, the superposition of the variables depends on whether they are geometric or hydrodynamic. In fact, as in the simulations the two stars never overlap, the new hydrodynamic variables are obtained from the simple sum, for every point of the grid, of the variables of the single stars. The superposition, following [Marronetti P., Tsatsin P. 2013], of the geometric variables of the two stars is instead given by:

$$\alpha = \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 - 1 \quad (6.4)$$

$$\beta^i = \beta_1^i + \beta_2^i \quad (6.5)$$

$$\gamma_{ij} = \gamma_{ij1} + \gamma_{ij2} - \eta_{ij} \quad (6.6)$$

where the subscripts 1 and 2 indicate the variables for the first and the second star respectively, while η_{ij} refers to the standard Minkowski metric. In particular, the first two equations establish the lapse function and the shift vector of the new setup, the third equation describes the new spatial metric which still asymptotically tends to the Minkowski limit.

6.4 The single star case

Before testing the superposition of 2 TOV solutions, the single neutron star case has been treated in order to estimate the constraint violations both without and with the solver enabled. Therefore, the first studies are referred to an object constructed using the APR4 equation of state [Pandharipande V. R., Akmal A., Ravenhall D. G., 1998] and a central rest mass density of $6 \cdot 10^{17}$ kg/m³; at this initial state, the CT_MULTILEVEL solver is not set on. The first grid setup, a small one used to better show the most noteworthy variables, consists of a symmetric domain with sizes $[-8, +8]$ for both x,y and z, containing three superposed global levels, each with a spacing which is half of the previous one, and with spacing $dx = dy = dz = 1$ for the coarsest grid; due to the very few GB of RAM required (from 2 to 14 ca.), these simple simulations have been run on the INFN workstation Zenon of the university of Catania. The first graph is referred to the modeling of the object, in terms of its density expressed in units $G = c = M_{\odot} = 1$; for an easy visualization, both a 2D plot (made with the VisIt program, in remote visualization option) and a 1D plot of the density profile are shown:

Fig. 11 - Single TOV solution; the density is represented in the plane xy.

Fig. 12 - Single TOV solution; the density is represented along the x axis.

Fig. 13 - Single TOV solution; profile of the (x, x) component of the 3-metric.

It is interesting to notice that the density distribution does not depend on the implementation of the solver, as it will not modify the density in any case.

Fig. 13 shows the variation of the (x, x) component of the 3-metric along the x axis; the grid has been extended, covering the domain $[-80, 80]$ and still containing three superposed levels, with a spacing $dx = dy = dz = 2$ for the coarsest grid. The expected behavior of the function, according to the TOV solution (3.41), is reproduced; as one gets far from the center, where $m = 0$ and $g_{xx} = 1$, the mass function grows and so does the g_{xx} function. At $x = \pm 6$ ca., the surface of the star is reached and the mass function reaches the maximum value, corresponding to the total mass of the star M ; after this point, the behavior of the function depends entirely on the reciprocal of the radius.

At this point of the work, a first evaluation of the violation of the Hamiltonian constraint, whose absolute value is represented in logarithmic scale in Fig.14, has been carried out:

Fig. 14 - Violation of the Hamiltonian constraint for the initial data computed by PIZZATOV.

The violation is particularly high near the star boundaries, where a steep gradient of the functions is present, while it reaches the minimum values outside the star itself. The same quantity is shown in Fig.15, where the constraint violation is computed using the extended grid which has already been used in order to eval-

uate g_{xx} ; such a grid setup will also be used in order to model the binary star in the next chapter:

Fig. 15 - Violation of the Hamiltonian constraint evaluated on the extended grid.

At this point, the solver is implemented: in particular, the variables the equations are solved for are represented by the conformal factor ψ , with initial guess simply being $\psi = 1$, and the three components of the shift vector, with initial guess determined by TOVSTAR and stored in ADMBase; at the present state of the work, the solver acts on the three superposed levels which cover the whole grid. The action of the solver becomes clear when considering Fig. 16: the Hamiltonian constraint violation is evaluated on the x-axis, both with the solver disabled and with the solver enabled; in this last case, the solver relaxes 300 times on the bottom level, 50 on the top and 50 for every intermediate step. In particular, the absolute value of the violation is represented using a logarithmic scale, both with the solver disabled (red line) and with the solver enabled (green line).

Fig. 16 - Comparison of the Hamiltonian constraint violation - one-dimensional plot.

The violation now reaches its peak, which is three orders of magnitude lower than the previous one, in correspondence of the center of the star and tends to zero when moving away. The possibility of further lowering the constraint violation is now explored and the results are shown in the next three figures; in particular, the iterations on the bottom level have been modified and the three cases 100, 300 and 1000 iterations have been analyzed. Due to the increase of the computational power required (which ranges now from 100 to 1000 GB of RAM), these simulations have been run on the Marconi supercomputer.

Fig. 17 - Violation of the Hamiltonian constraint with 100 iterations on the bottom level.

Fig. 18 - Violation of the Hamiltonian constraint with 300 iterations on the bottom level.

Fig. 19- Violation of the Hamiltonian constraint with 1000 iterations on the bottom level.

As it has been described before, modifying the original TOV solution, e.g. by enabling an orbital velocity or superposing two solutions, results in the worsening of the violation of the Hamiltonian constraint. While the second case will be treated in detail in the next chapter, the first case is now studied; therefore, the solver has been disabled and the star has been boosted with an orbital velocity $v = 0.1c$ directed along the positive y axis. The new Hamiltonian constraint violation is represented in Fig. 20.

Fig. 20 - Violation of the Hamiltonian constraint for a single star with orbital velocity $v = 0.1c$.

As expected, the constraint violation has clearly worsened, and now extends its maximum values all over the star. The introduction of a non-zero velocity also allows to estimate the violation of the momentum constraints; in the stationary case, in fact, it is immediate to observe that these constraints are zero everywhere, and this behavior is reproduced in the simulations. In particular, the presence of an orbital velocity along y “enables” all the components of the momentum constraint, not just the second one. Fig. 21 is referred to the computation of the three momentum constraints still in absence of the solver; in addition, while the first and the second component of the momentum constraint have been evaluated on the xy plane, the evaluation of the third component is referred to the yz plane, as it is identically zero in every point of the xy plane.

Fig. 21 - Violation of the momentum constraints for the initial data computed by PIZZATOV.

As it has been done for the case without velocity, the action of the solver has been evaluated. The levels and the iterations on the top and the intermediate levels have been left as before, while the number of relaxations on the bottom level has been set to 500; therefore, the Hamiltonian constraint violation is represented in the following Fig. 22

Fig. 22 - Violation of the Hamiltonian constraint after 500 iterations on the bottom level.

The solver, which now has to solve all the four equations simultaneously, has lowered once again the maximum constraint violation and the same action is found when computing the violation on the components of the momentum constraint, which have been represented in Fig. 23; again, the first two components are evaluated on the xy plane, while the third component refers to the yz plane. Of particular note is the fact that, in this case, the solver doesn't immediately homogenize the violations and, at the same time, its action has decreased effectiveness; it is, in fact, still evident, for each graph, a central feature constituting the region with the highest violation. This may principally depend on the fact that the problem the solver has to solve has increased its complexity, so that is in general more difficult to achieve convergence.

Fig. 23 - Violation of the momentum constraints after 500 iterations on the bottom level.

6.5 The binary star case

After considering the application of the solver to the single TOV solution, the binary star case has been studied. Two TOV solutions, still computed through the PIZZATO module using the APR4 EOS and a central rest mass density of $6 \cdot 10^{17} \text{kg/m}^3$ and superposed in a single $[-80,80]$ domain containing three global levels and 2 local levels with domains $[-30,30]$ and $[-20,20]$ respectively, with spacing $dx = dy = dz = 2$ for the coarsest grid, are implemented, with centers at $x = \pm 30$. The case has been treated similarly to what has been done for the single star: the first step has regarded the study of the density distribution in order to evaluate the correct implementation of the two stars, which, at this point of the work, have no velocity and are still not treated with the solver. This case is often referred to as “head-on binary”: as no orbital velocities are present, in fact, the enablement of time evolution would make the two stars collide head-on, with the result of a single final object.

Fig. 24 - Binary star system; the density is represented in the plane xy .

As expected, the density distribution of the single star is not altered by the presence of the second star. The same does not happen for the geometric variables, which are instead modified by the superposition; the most remarkable case is represented by the 3-dimensional metric, whose profile of the (x, x) component is again represented in the following one-dimensional plot:

Fig. 25 - Binary star system; profile of the (x, x) component of the 3-metric.

It is immediate to recognize that the presence of the second star has raised the values of the metric component in every point of the grid and, in particular, in the region between the two stars, according to eq. (6.6). The superposition has also acted, as anticipated before, on the violation of the Hamiltonian constraint, represented in Fig. 26; as it happened in the single star case with the velocity enabled, the maximum constraint violation is reached not only on the boundaries of the stars but has also propagated all over the entire star regions.

Once again, the action of the solver has then been considered before also adding orbital velocities to the binary. A setup consisting of 100 iterations on the bottom level, 50 on the intermediate ones and 50 on the top level has been used. Once again, the solver acts on all the grids present in the domain, both global and local.

Fig. 26 - Binary star system; violation of the Hamiltonian constraint.

Fig. 27 - Binary star system; violation of the Hamiltonian constraint with 100 iterations on the bottom level.

While the action of the solver has allowed to obtain results which are similar to the ones observed for the single star case, the introduction of local grids has worsened the constraint violation on its boundaries; this violation, however, is limited to the boundaries and hasn't propagated, so it could be neglected.

At this point of the work, orbital velocities have also been added and the final case, consisting of the binary star with orbital velocities and with the solver enabled, is presented; in particular, the star with center at $x = -30$ has been boosted with a velocity $v = 0.1c$ directed along the positive y axis, while a velocity with the same module but opposite direction has been used for the other star. The solver setup has been left unchanged. The violations to the four constraints are evaluated and presented in Fig. 28 and 29:

Fig. 28 - Binary star system; violation of the Hamiltonian constraint with 100 iterations on the bottom level.

Fig. 29 - Binary star system; violation of the Hamiltonian constraint with 100 iterations on the bottom level.

Chapter 7

Conclusions

In this thesis work, the first application of the `CT_MULTILEVEL` solver to the binary neutron star case has been presented. The work has involved the extension and use of the `TOVSTAR` program as a module of the Einstein Toolkit; the same has been modified in order to superpose two TOV solutions and add orbital velocities to the same. The application of the `CT_MULTILEVEL` solver has been done subsequently both on the single star case and on the binary star system; in both cases the action has been evaluated with and without velocities enabled.

It has been determined that, for the single star case without velocity, the solver acts as expected; the study which has been presented has shown that, increasing the number of iterations on the coarsest grid, the Hamiltonian constraint violation, which is highest in correspondence of the star boundaries, becomes progressively lower and tends to be globally homogeneous. The introduction of a velocity alters the TOV solution, and, as the new result is in general more distant from the analytic solution of the Einstein field equations, the violation of the constraints, which are now including also the momentum constraints, becomes higher in the star region. The solver has again lowered the violations, but the presence of the velocity dampens its effectiveness, leaving a lesser resolved feature. This, however, is not surprising: the number of differential equations `CT_MULTILEVEL` now has to simultaneously solve has increased from one to four.

The binary star case has demonstrated to be consistent with the results obtained in the single star case; when both the velocities and the solver are not enabled, the maximum values of the Hamiltonian constraint violation have extended to the entire regions occupied by the stars; this is, again, an expected behavior, as the superposition of the two stars is not an analytic solution of the Einstein's equations. Activating the solver again lowers the constraint violation, similarly to what happens for the single star. The velocity addition also shows the same effects: the Hamiltonian constraint violation increases and the three

momentum constraints are enabled. Once again, the solver acts lowering the violation but the regions of the stars are not completely resolved as before. The suspicion is then that the solver hasn't converged yet; increasing the number of iterations may help in this sense, and further studies are in progress.

The work has proven the stability of `CT_MULTILEVEL` when working with the new binary neutron star setup. Particularly noteworthy is the fact that the solver has also been tested with the most significant and complex configurations; the possibility to work with the Marconi supercomputer has proven, in this sense, essential. Pending its availability and the corresponding turnaround time for simulations, which is often an issue in large supercomputing systems, many more studies are currently under way and will help optimizing the solver setup.

As the purpose of the work is to provide a new way to construct initial data available within the next versions of the Einstein Toolkit, further studies will be carried out in order to improve the effectiveness of the solver and to ensure the capability of the same to work in the most general conditions. For example, other programs instead of `TOVSTAR` may be used in order to test different initial conditions for the neutron stars. A comparison between solvers is also possible; in particular, the same initial guess may be used both with `CT_MULTILEVEL` and with other solvers, e.g. the public software `LORENE` which is also implemented as a module for the Einstein Toolkit. Moreover, as this work has been carried out principally to demonstrate the viability of the solver for binary neutron star systems initial data, no attention has been given to the creation of astrophysically realistic systems; in general, in fact, the two neutron stars are rotating and do not have the same mass. In addition, hydrodynamic equilibrium of the two stars should also be considered: the stars are, in fact, implemented in a very simple way, as the variables are just "copied" into the various grid points; as a consequence of this fact, when time evolution is enabled, a matter redistribution takes place in each of the two stars, giving rise to a spurious gravitational signal, which disappears when equilibrium is reached.

Finally, it is also intention of the collaboration to enable the time evolution for the initial data generated with this new method, in order to extract gravitational waveforms which could, in the future, be used for gravitational wave astronomy.

Chapter 8

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The bibliography is organized in such a way that the sources are presented in consultation order.

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Appendices

Appendix A

Wave Equation Solver

```
#include <stdio.h>
#include <stdlib.h>
#include <math.h>

#define PI 3.14159265

typedef struct {
    int r;
    int c;
    float**a; } matrix;

main (){
    int i ,j ,I ,J , scelta ;
    float u ,deltax ,deltat ,deltax2 ,deltat2 ,deltax4 ,deltat4 ;
    float l ,r ;
    float Q,N,D;
    float xmin=0.0 ,xmax=10*PI;
    float tmin=0.0;
    float lambda;
    printf ("          FDA 1-d WAVE EQUATION - Antonio Figura \n \n");
    printf("Inserire il numero di suddivisioni lungo l'asse spaziale \n");
    scanf ("%d",&J);
    deltax=10*PI/J;
    printf ("Ogni suddivisione spaziale ha ampiezza %f \n", deltax);
    printf ("Inserire il numero di Courant, minore di 1 \n");
    scanf ("%f", &lambda);
    deltat=lambda*deltax;
```

```

printf ("Ogni suddivisione temporale ha ampiezza %f \n", deltat);
printf ("Inserire il numero di iterazioni temporali \n");
scanf ("%d", &I);
matrix mat;
mat.r=I+1;
mat.c=J+1;
mat.a= malloc (mat.r * sizeof (int*));
    for (i=0;i<mat.r;i++)
mat.a[i]=malloc (mat.c * sizeof (int));
    for (j=0;j<mat.c;j++) {
mat.a[0][j]= sin (0.0 +j*deltax) ;}
mat.a[0][J]= 0.0;
    for (j=0;j<mat.c;j++)
mat.a[1][j]=-cos (0.0 +j*deltax);
}
    for (i=2;i<mat.r;i++) {
mat.a[i][0]=2*mat.a[i-1][0]-mat.a[i-2][0]+
lambda*lambda*(mat.a[i-1][1]-2*mat.a[i-1][0]+mat.a[i-1][J-1]);
    for (j=1;j<mat.c;j++) {
mat.a[i][j]=2*mat.a[i-1][j]-mat.a[i-2][j]+
lambda*lambda*(mat.a[i-1][j+1]-2*mat.a[i-1][j]+mat.a[i-1][j-1]) ;}
mat.a[i][J]= mat.a[i][0];
}
    for (i=0;i<mat.r;i++) {
        for (j=0;j<mat.c;j++) {
printf (" %f  ", mat.a[i][j]);}
printf ("\n");
}
////////////////////////////////////
deltax2=2*deltax;
deltat2=lambda*deltax2;
matrix mat2;
mat2.r=I+1;
mat2.c=(J/2)+1;
mat2.a= malloc (mat2.r * sizeof (int*));
for (i=0;i<mat2.r;i++)
    mat2.a[i]=malloc (mat2.c * sizeof (int));
    for (j=0;j<mat2.c;j++) {
        mat2.a[0][j]= sin (0.0 +j*deltax2) ;}
mat.a[0][J/2]= 0.0;

```

```

    for (j=0;j<mat2.c;j++) {
        mat2.a[1][j]=-cos(0.0+j*deltax2);
    }
    for (i=2;i<mat2.r;i++) {
        mat2.a[i][0]=2*mat2.a[i-1][0]-mat2.a[i-2][0]+
        lambda*lambda*(mat2.a[i-1][1]-2*mat2.a[i-1][0]+mat2.a[i-1][(J/2)-1]);
        for (j=1;j<mat2.c;j++) {
            mat2.a[i][j]=2*mat2.a[i-1][j]-mat2.a[i-2][j]+
            lambda*lambda*(mat2.a[i-1][j+1]-2*mat2.a[i-1][j]+mat2.a[i-1][j-1]);
            mat2.a[i][J/2]= mat2.a[i][0];
        }
    }
    //////////////////////////////////////
    deltax4=4*deltax;
    deltat4=lambda*deltax4;
    matrix mat4;
    mat4.r=I+1;
    mat4.c=(J/4)+1;
    mat4.a= malloc (mat4.r * sizeof (int*));
    for (i=0;i<mat4.r;i++)
        mat4.a[i]=malloc (mat4.c * sizeof (int));
        for (j=0;j<mat4.c;j++) {
            mat4.a[0][j]= sin(0.0+j*deltax4);
        }
        for (j=0;j<mat4.c;j++) {
            mat4.a[1][j]=-cos(0.0+j*deltax4);
        }
    for (i=2;i<mat4.r;i++) {
        mat4.a[i][0]=2*mat4.a[i-1][0]-mat4.a[i-2][0]+
        lambda*lambda*(mat4.a[i-1][1]-2*mat4.a[i-1][0]+mat4.a[i-1][(J/4)-1]);
        for (j=1;j<mat4.c;j++) {
            mat4.a[i][j]=2*mat4.a[i-1][j]-mat4.a[i-2][j]+
            lambda*lambda*(mat4.a[i-1][j+1]-2*mat4.a[i-1][j]+mat4.a[i-1][j-1]);
            mat4.a[i][J/4]= mat4.a[i][0];
        }
    }
    //////////////////////////////////////
    printf ("\n \n");
    printf("Esecuzione del test di Richardson \n");
    // Test Localizzato //
    /*
    N=0;
    D=0;

```

```

for (j=1;j<(J/4);j++){
    i=0;
    N=fabsf(mat4.a[i][j]-mat2.a[i][j]);
    D=fabsf(mat2.a[i][j]-mat.a[i][j]);
    Q=(N)/(D);
    printf (" Iterazione %d , Q= %f ", j, Q);
    printf ("\n");
}
*/
N=0;
D=0;
for (i=0;i<mat.r;i++) {
    for (j=1;j<(J/4);j++) {
        N=N+(mat4.a[i][j]-mat2.a[i][2*j])*(mat4.a[i][j]-mat2.a[i][2*j]);
        D=D+(mat2.a[i][2*j]-mat.a[i][4*j])*(mat2.a[i][2*j]-mat.a[i][4*j]);
    }
}
Q=sqrt(N)/sqrt(D);
printf (" Iterazione %d , Q= %f ", i, Q);
printf ("\n");
}
FILE * f;
f=fopen (" data.dat", "w");
for (j=0;j<mat.c;j++) {
    fprintf (f, " %f ", j*deltax);{
    for (i=0;i<mat.r;i++) {
        fprintf (f, " %f ", mat.a[i][j]);}
    fprintf (f," \n");}
}
f=fopen (" data2.dat", "w");
for (j=0;j<mat2.c;j++) {
    fprintf (f, " %f ", 2*j*deltax);{
    for (i=0;i<mat2.r;i++) {
        fprintf (f, " %f ", mat2.a[i][j]);}
    fprintf (f," \n");}
}
f=fopen (" data4.dat", "w");
for (j=0;j<mat4.c;j++) {
    fprintf (f, " %f ", 4*j*deltax);{
    for (i=0;i<mat4.r;i++) {
        fprintf (f, " %f ", mat4.a[i][j]);}
}

```

```
    fprintf (f, "\n");  
}  
system ("pause");  
}
```

Appendix B

The Conformal Thin Sandwich equations

The momentum and Hamiltonian constraint equations determined in chapter 5.3 are, respectively:

$$(\tilde{\Delta}_L \beta)^i - (\tilde{L}\beta)^{ij} \tilde{D}_j \ln(\tilde{\alpha}) = \tilde{\alpha} \tilde{D}_j (\tilde{\alpha}^{-1} \tilde{u}^{ij}) + \frac{4}{3} \tilde{\alpha} \psi^6 \tilde{D}^i K + 16\pi \tilde{\alpha} \psi^{10} S^i \quad (\text{B.1})$$

$$\tilde{D}^2 \psi - \frac{1}{8} \psi \tilde{R} - \frac{1}{12} \psi^5 K^2 + \frac{1}{8} \psi^{-7} \tilde{A}_{ij} \tilde{A}^{ij} = -2\pi \psi^5 \rho \quad (\text{B.2})$$

The four equations can be simplified by assuming the following three hypotheses:

$$\gamma_{ij} = \psi^4 \delta_{ij} \quad (\text{B.3})$$

i.e. the hypothesis of *conformal flatness*, which consists in the assumption that the conformal metric is represented by the Minkowski metric;

$$K = 0 \quad (\text{B.4})$$

which is the condition of *Maximal Slicing*, and

$$\tilde{u}_{ij} = 0 \quad (\text{B.5})$$

for every value of i and j from 1 to 3. Equations (B.1) and (B.2) are then cast in the following form

$$(\tilde{\Delta}_L \beta)^i - (\tilde{L}\beta)^{ij} \tilde{D}_j \ln(\tilde{\alpha}) - 16\pi \tilde{\alpha} \psi^{10} S^i = 0 \quad (\text{B.6})$$

$$\tilde{D}^2 \psi + \frac{1}{8} \psi^{-7} \tilde{A}_{ij} \tilde{A}^{ij} + 2\pi \psi^5 \rho = 0 \quad (\text{B.7})$$

with:

$$\tilde{A}^{ij} = \frac{1}{2\tilde{\alpha}}(\tilde{L}\beta)^{ij} \quad (\text{B.8})$$

$$(\tilde{\Delta}_L\beta)^i = \tilde{D}^2\beta^i + \frac{1}{3}\tilde{D}^i\tilde{D}_j\beta^j \quad (\text{B.9})$$

$$(\tilde{L}\beta)^{ij} = \tilde{D}^i\beta^j + \tilde{D}^j\beta^i - \frac{2}{3}\delta^{ij}\tilde{D}_k\beta^k \quad (\text{B.10})$$

$$\tilde{\alpha} = \psi^{-6}\alpha \quad (\text{B.11})$$

$$S^i = -\psi^{-4}\delta^{ij}n^\mu T_{j\mu} = (\rho + p)v^i \quad (\text{B.12})$$

$$\tilde{D}_i = \partial_i \quad (\text{B.13})$$

Explicitly, the above turns into the following system for ψ , β^x, β^y and β^z :

$$\partial_{xx}\psi + \partial_{yy}\psi + \partial_{zz}\psi + \frac{\tilde{A}^2}{8}\psi^{-7} + 2\pi\rho\psi^5 = 0 \quad (\text{B.14})$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{4}{3}\partial_{xx}\beta^x + \partial_{yy}\beta^y + \partial_{zz}\beta^z + \frac{1}{3}(\partial_{xy}\beta^y\partial_{xz}\beta^z) \\ & - \left(\frac{4}{3}\partial_x\beta^x - \frac{2}{3}\partial_y\beta^y - \frac{2}{3}\partial_z\beta^z\right) \left(\frac{1}{\alpha}\partial_x\alpha - 6\frac{1}{\psi}\partial_x\psi\right) \\ & - (\partial_y\beta^x + \partial_x\beta^y) \left(\frac{1}{\alpha}\partial_y\alpha - 6\frac{1}{\psi}\partial_y\psi\right) \\ & - (\partial_z\beta^x + \partial_x\beta^z) \left(\frac{1}{\alpha}\partial_z\alpha - 6\frac{1}{\psi}\partial_z\psi\right) \\ & - 16\pi\alpha\psi^4 S^x = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.15})$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{4}{3}\partial_{yy}\beta^y + \partial_{xx}\beta^x + \partial_{zz}\beta^z + \frac{1}{3}(\partial_{yx}\beta^x\partial_{yz}\beta^z) \\ & - \left(\frac{4}{3}\partial_y\beta^y - \frac{2}{3}\partial_x\beta^x - \frac{2}{3}\partial_z\beta^z\right) \left(\frac{1}{\alpha}\partial_y\alpha - 6\frac{1}{\psi}\partial_y\psi\right) \\ & - (\partial_x\beta^y + \partial_y\beta^x) \left(\frac{1}{\alpha}\partial_x\alpha - 6\frac{1}{\psi}\partial_x\psi\right) \\ & - (\partial_z\beta^y + \partial_y\beta^z) \left(\frac{1}{\alpha}\partial_z\alpha - 6\frac{1}{\psi}\partial_z\psi\right) \\ & - 16\pi\alpha\psi^4 S^y = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.16})$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{4}{3}\partial_{zz}\beta^z + \partial_{xx}\beta^x + \partial_{yy}\beta^y + \frac{1}{3}(\partial_{zx}\beta^x\partial_{zy}\beta^y) \\
& - \left(\frac{4}{3}\partial_z\beta^z - \frac{2}{3}\partial_x\beta^x - \frac{2}{3}\partial_y\beta^y\right) \left(\frac{1}{\alpha}\partial_z\alpha - 6\frac{1}{\psi}\partial_z\psi\right) \\
& - (\partial_x\beta^z + \partial_z\beta^x) \left(\frac{1}{\alpha}\partial_x\alpha - 6\frac{1}{\psi}\partial_x\psi\right) \\
& - (\partial_y\beta^z + \partial_z\beta^y) \left(\frac{1}{\alpha}\partial_y\alpha - 6\frac{1}{\psi}\partial_y\psi\right) \\
& - 16\pi\alpha\psi^4 S^z = 0
\end{aligned} \tag{B.17}$$

with:

$$\tilde{A}^2 = \psi^8(A^{xx2} + A^{yy2} + A^{zz2} + 2A^{xy2} + 2A^{xz2} + 2A^{yz2}) \tag{B.18}$$

$$A^{xx} = \frac{\psi^6}{2\alpha} \left(\frac{4}{3}\partial_x\beta^x - \frac{2}{3}\partial_y\beta^y - \frac{2}{3}\partial_z\beta^z\right) \tag{B.19}$$

$$A^{xy} = \frac{\psi^6}{2\alpha}(\partial_x\beta^y + \partial_y\beta^x) \tag{B.20}$$

$$A^{xz} = \frac{\psi^6}{2\alpha}(\partial_x\beta^z + \partial_z\beta^x) \tag{B.21}$$

$$A^{yy} = \frac{\psi^6}{2\alpha} \left(\frac{4}{3}\partial_y\beta^y - \frac{2}{3}\partial_x\beta^x - \frac{2}{3}\partial_z\beta^z\right) \tag{B.22}$$

$$A^{yz} = \frac{\psi^6}{2\alpha}(\partial_y\beta^z + \partial_z\beta^y) \tag{B.23}$$

$$A^{zz} = \frac{\psi^6}{2\alpha} \left(\frac{4}{3}\partial_z\beta^z - \frac{2}{3}\partial_x\beta^x - \frac{2}{3}\partial_y\beta^y\right) \tag{B.24}$$

$$S^x = (\rho + p)v^x \tag{B.25}$$

$$S^y = (\rho + p)v^y \tag{B.26}$$

$$S^z = (\rho + p)v^z \tag{B.27}$$

$$b = \beta_i v^i = \psi^4(\beta^x v^x + \beta^y v^y + \beta^z v^z) \tag{B.28}$$

$$v^i = \frac{u^i}{\alpha u^0} + \frac{\beta^i}{\alpha} \tag{B.29}$$